

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D5.1

1st Report - New Approach Methodologies (NAMs)

Based on AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritized endpoints

WP5 – T 5.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

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¹ PU = Public

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Abstract

WP5, as part of its task 5.2, is developing, optimizing and evaluating the relevance of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for the assessment of (eco)toxicological endpoints such as non-genotoxic carcinogenicity (NGTxC), (developmental) neurotoxicity (DNT), immunotoxicity and endocrine disruption (ED), in particular thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD) and metabolic endocrine disruption (MD). This deliverable provides a synthesis of the current regulatory needs related to NAMs for risk assessment, describes how the methods being developed in WP5 contribute to these needs and the steps WP5 is taking to measure the improvement of the regulatory readiness of the methods. An exhaustive list of the assays under development among the twelve projects in WP5 is presented in Annex I for human health and environmental hazard assessment. The inventory of NAMs presented in this deliverable will support robust development of IATA (Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment) for the selected (eco)toxicological endpoints, and illustrates the role played by WP5 in the development of regulatory relevant NAMs.

Key Words

New Approach Methodologies (NAMs); Human health assessment; Environmental toxicity assessment; Regulatory relevance; Non-genotoxic carcinogenicity (NGTxC); Developmental neurotoxicity (DNT); Adult neurotoxicity (ANT); Immunotoxicity; Endocrine disruption: Thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD); Metabolic (endocrine) disruptive effects (MD).

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Authors and Acknowledgements

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Acronyms

3R: Reduction, Refinement and Replacement

ANT: Adult Neurotoxicity

AOP: Adverse Outcome Pathway

DNT: Developmental Neurotoxicity

ECHA: European Chemicals Agency

ED: Endocrine Disrupters

ED-Th: Endocrine disruptive effects – thyroid

EOGRTS: Extended one-generation reproductive toxicity study

IATA: Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment

IVB: *In vitro* test battery

KEs: Key Events

MDC: Metabolic disrupting chemicals

MIEs: Molecular Initiating Events

MOA: Mode Of Action

NAMs: New Approach Methodologies

NGTxC: Non genotoxic carcinogenicity

OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

T/ TL: Task/ Task co-leaders

THSD: Thyroid hormone system disruptor

WP/ WPL: Work Package/ WP co-leader

1. Introduction

PARC Work Package 5 has been establishing comprehensive testing strategies, thereby promoting the availability and applicability of new approach methodologies (NAMs) in risk assessment to improve the current hazard characterization paradigm (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023).

Although NAMs definition varies depending on the context, WP5 considers NAMs to be broadly based on the 3Rs principles (Reduce, Refine, Replace), rather than focusing solely on the non-use of animals. As agreed with colleagues from WP6, the definition accepted for the purpose of this deliverable is the following:

“New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) are defined as any valid and relevant technology, methodology, approach, strategies, or combination thereof that can provide information on chemical hazard, exposure, and risk assessment to reduce, refine or replace animal testing” (Roth N., Bearth A., 2023).

Newly established or optimized NAMs will support the establishment of the causality between toxicant and hazard manifestation and identification of how the toxicity happens (Hartung *et al.*, 2013), and their potential utility for regulatory purposes will be investigated within PARC (e.g., through AOP development and IATAs in WP5 and WP6).

WP 5 is organized into three different Tasks. Task 5.1 is focused on filling data gaps on specific (groups of) substances (Natural Toxins and BPA alternatives); A5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health and A5.1.2 Toxicity assessment addressing data gaps of concern for the environment) for five selected endpoints: non genotoxic carcinogenicity (NGTxC), endocrine disruptive effects - thyroid (ED-Th), metabolic endocrine disruption (Metabolic ED), immunotoxicity (ImmunoTox) and neurotoxicity (Neurotox). In Task 5.1. NAMs are being used to fill up data gaps when established guidelines are missing (OECD test guideline or EFSA/ECHA guidance). Task 5.3 improves the mechanistic understanding of toxicity by applying systems toxicology approaches (including: AOPs, PBK model development). Task 5.2 evaluates the relevance and readiness of new technologies, for the assessment of (eco)toxicological endpoints such as non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, immunotoxicity, endocrine disruption effects and (developmental) neurotoxicity, leveraging the OECD's AOP framework and AOPs developed in PARC (Task 5.3).

Examples of the technologies assessed are genomic, transcriptomic, proteomic, high-content analysis microscopy, high-resolution mass spectrometry, and human inducible pluripotent stem cell technology. Additionally, test methods, tools and methodologies will be developed to identify drivers of toxicity in mixtures and to support the grouping of chemicals, including the application of read across.

Furthermore, this task aims for the development and application of predictive *in vitro* and *in silico* tools to identify and characterise specific hazards. Through close collaboration with human biomonitoring communities in- and outside PARC, methods and computational approaches will be developed to study the metabolism of chemical substances in different biological (test) systems or matrices (e.g. cells, organoids, organs, blood) for comparison between species (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023).

The aim of this deliverable is to provide a synthesis of the current regulatory needs related to NAMs for risk assessment and to describe how the methods being developed within WP5 contribute to addressing these needs. However, as we are in the first phase of PARC, it is outside the scope of this deliverable to assess or evaluate the readiness for validation of these methods. A list of the assays under development among the twelve projects in WP5 is presented in Annex I, sorted by the five prioritised endpoints in the case of human health (NGTxCs, ED-Th, Metabolic ED, ImmunoTox and developmental/adult Neurotox) and mixed in the case of environment. The contribution of each method to address the regulatory needs have been summarized in Human Health before the table and clarified in the subheadings, and in Environment, is added in the table per assay.

2. Regulatory relevance

The regulatory relevance of the NAMs per endpoints addressed within WP5 projects has been extensively described in each of their project descriptions and their potential contribution to specific regulations or policy processes has been summarized in this chapter.

Neurotoxicity

Developmental (DNT) and adult (ANT) neurotoxicity are currently assessed via different OECD guideline studies and with different REACH standard information requirements. DNT/ANT guideline studies are extraordinarily resource-intensive and therefore not suited for studying the adverse effects of large numbers of chemicals. Therefore, there is an international consensus, strongly supported by EFSA and the OECD, that DNT testing must be faster and more human-relevant by implementing an alternative DNT testing battery for regulatory purposes. The current state-of-the-art is the use of rat *in vivo* studies (e.g. OECD TG426) that do not cover all aspects of human brain development. Hence this should be replaced by a DNT *in vitro* test battery (DNT IVB), which comprises of several human- and rat-based *in vitro* test methods covering key neurodevelopmental processes, e.g., neural progenitor cell proliferation, differentiation of neurons and oligodendrocytes, and apoptosis. While this represents a step forward towards establishing an alternative DNT testing regime, there are critical neurotoxicity steps not covered (gaps) in the DNT IVB, including human synaptogenesis, human neural network formation, myelination, and behavioural correlates for the rodent *in vivo* studies including behaviour, sensory function, learning and memory endpoints.

Under REACH, standard information requirements that inform on adult neurotoxicity include 8.5.1 Acute toxicity (Annex VII), 8.5.2 or 8.5.3 Acute toxicity (Annex VIII), 8.6.1 Short-term repeated dose toxicity study (28 days) (Annex VIII), and 8.6.2. Sub-chronic toxicity study (90-day) (Annex IX). Also under REACH, standard information requirements that may inform on developmental neurotoxicity include 8.7.1. Screening for reproductive/developmental toxicity (OECD TG 421 or TG 422) (Annex VIII), 8.7.2. Pre-natal developmental toxicity study (OECD TG 414) on a first species (Annex IX), 8.7.3. Extended One-Generation Reproductive Toxicity Study (OECD TG 443) (potentially triggered at Annex IX, and a standard requirement at Annex X), and 8.7.2. Pre-natal developmental toxicity study (OECD TG 414) in a second species (Annex X). Under REACH Annexes IX and X, elements from the OECD TG 426: Developmental Neurotoxicity Study may be used to extend the Test No. 443: Extended One-Generation Reproductive Toxicity Study.

Metabolic Endocrine Disruption

Despite metabolic disrupting chemicals (MDC) being suspected to play a major role in the worldwide epidemics of metabolic disorders, there are currently no specific regulatory *in vivo* or *in vitro* tests allowing to identify their adverse effects. Rodent bioassays currently in use may not fully cover human physiology as there are several receptors involved (e.g. CAR or PXR) that are known to show species differences. Since the absence of suitable and specific mechanistic test methods prohibits hazard and risk assessment of chemicals to determine their potential for metabolic disruption, the development of such test methods has been internationally recognized as a high priority. Screening assays for relevant nuclear receptors, which bind certain MDCs and therefore constitute an early event in the molecular pathogenesis of some metabolic disruption related pathways, are underway (Manibusan and Touart, 2017), but there is also a need for *in vitro* methods that can cover endpoints corresponding to adverse outcomes of metabolic disruption with relevance to human health (Braeuning et al., 2023).

Non Genotoxic Carcinogenicity

Genotoxic compounds induce DNA damage, which can be detected by an established *in vitro* and *in vivo* battery of genotoxicity assays. For NGTxCs, DNA is not the primary target, and the possible modes of action (MoA) of NGTxCs are much more diverse than those of genotoxic compounds, and there is no specific *in vitro* assay for detecting NGTxCs. In the different EU regulations (e.g. food safety: Reg EC 1272/2008, Reg EC 1107/2009), carcinogenicity is evaluated in long-term (2-year) exposure studies with rodents (TG451, TG453), in combination with *in vitro* and *in vivo* genotoxicity testing (TG475, TG474, , TG470, TG488). However, long-term exposure rodent bioassays are time-consuming, costly, ethically questionable, and considered of limited relevance for humans (Madia et al., 2019). Indeed, some mechanisms induced by NGTxCs display biological

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and physiological species differences affecting the human relevance of the *in vivo* (intraperitoneal rodent) test results (Heusinkveld et al., 2020a). Since less than 5% of chemicals registered worldwide have been tested in long-term carcinogenicity rodent studies (Doe et al., 2019), there is an urgent need for a transition to new approach methodologies (NAMs). This allows for the inclusion of human-relevant *in vitro* and *in silico* methods that enable using recent advances in our understanding of diseases and employ the latest non-animal methods available in a modern safety assessment toolbox (Audebert et al., 2023).

Endocrine Disruption - Thyroid

The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) and EFSA based the regulatory guidance for evaluating biocides and pesticides for endocrine disrupting activity on the revised OECD Guidance Document 150 (OECD 2018). Despite these relatively recent advances, current test strategies and regulations are inadequate regarding specifically identifying thyroid hormone system disruptors (THSDs) for conducting the robust chemical risk assessment required for regulation. The tests rely heavily on histopathological changes in rodent thyroid glands or measuring changes in systemic TH levels, but they lack specific new approach methodologies (NAMs) that can adequately detect TH-mediated effects such as changes in deiodinase activity or membrane transport of THs. Some *in vitro* assays (non-OECD TGs) for certain Molecular Initiating Events (MIEs) relevant for THSD are available and are currently in the process of regulatory validation (TSAR, Thyroid: <https://tsar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/thyroid/>). However, there is still a pressing need to develop more extensive test batteries of NAMs that cover a broader range of MIEs and Key Events (KEs) i.e. including the intermediate steps from MIE to Adverse Outcomes (AO). This includes effects on TH synthesis, TH metabolism and TH action in target tissues. See Ramhøj et al., 2023 for more details (<https://doi.org/10.3389/ftox.2023.1189303>)

Immunotoxicity

Currently under REACH, immunotoxicity investigations are triggered based on repeated dose toxicity studies (28- or 90-day) in cases where there are some indications of immunotoxicity. If indications of immunosuppression are seen, one can include e.g., Cohort 3 into the study design of EOGRTS (developmental immunotoxicity) (OECD TG 443) or request to have an immunotoxicity investigation included in a standard repeated dose toxicity study (adult immunotoxicity).

While respiratory sensitization is mentioned as a hazard in the CLP (Reg EC 1272/2008) regulation, it is acknowledged that there is no validated method to detect respiratory sensitizers available. Hence, a need to develop methods to detect respiratory sensitizers is recognized and a promising *in vitro* approach was published (Chary et al., 2019; Burla et al., 2023). On top of that the CLP regulation foresees that non-animal testing is conducted wherever possible, implying support for the development of NAMs.

Sensitization is analysed as part of the data requirements for plant protection products (Reg EC 1107/2009) and biocides (Reg EC 528/2012). The need to develop methods for respiratory sensitization as well as alternative testing strategies is recognized.

On the OCED level a limited number of *in vitro* immunotoxicity assessment methods have achieved the stage of OECD test guidelines (https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/environment/oecd-guidelines-for-the-testing-of-chemicals-section-4-health-effects_20745788). Currently, a DRP on respiratory sensitization is being developed. Also, some non-stand-alone methods have been validated for specific immunotoxic endpoints: (IL-2 assay, OECD (2023), *Test No. 444A: In Vitro Immunotoxicity: IL-2 Luc Assay*, OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 4, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/27b10ba3-en>). Respiratory sensitisation currently relies almost solely on human data, and ALIsens® and GardAir, the only available NAMs, have not been formally validated.

When it comes to the immunotoxic effects of natural toxins, which are researched as part of the work done in WP5, the knowledge of the immunotoxic properties of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins is significantly limited, with the NAMs being developed and used are expected to fill up data gaps for hazard assessment (WoE, grouping approaches). Enniatins are a class of organic chemical compounds found in *Fusarium* fungi. They appear in nature as mixtures of cyclic depsipeptides, *Alternaria* is a genus of Deuteromycetes fungi. All species are known as major plant pathogens. They are also common allergens in humans, growing indoors and causing hay fever or hypersensitivity reactions that sometimes lead to asthma. Existing *in vitro* studies have focused on testing a constrained set of toxins, as the option to chemically synthesise these toxins was limited. Furthermore,

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the few available *in vitro* studies have produced conflicting results. These natural toxins currently have no regulations due to limited knowledge regarding their toxicity, including lung immune-modulating effects.

Environment

The following regulatory fields have been identified to benefit from the outcomes of the development of innovative methods and tools for environmental toxicology and ecotoxicology testing and modelling:

- CLP regulation (Reg. (EC) No 1272/2008), the plant-protection-products (Reg. (EC) 1107/2009, Reg. (EC) 283/2013) and biocides regulations (Reg. (EU) No 528/2012) or the REACH regulation (Reg. (EC) No 1907/2006) (Weight of Evidence, read-across and grouping approaches).
- EFSA/ECHA Guidance for the identification of endocrine disruptors in the context of Regulations (EU) No 528/2012 and (EC) No 1107/2009.
- EU Green Deal: early identification of environmental hazardous properties with MoA-based ecotoxicity NAMs, data from NAMs could be used for prioritization of chemicals for more detailed Environmental Risk Assessment.
- EU Framework for Endocrine Disruptors (COM/2018/734 final): Tests covering other aspects of the endocrine system or other animal groups still need to be developed and/or validated.
- EU Strategy for Pharmaceuticals in the Environment (COM (2019) 128 final): Support research on monitoring individual substances and mixtures of substances in fresh and marine waters, soils, sediments, and wildlife, using conventional analytical and complementary techniques.
- EU Water Framework Directive - WFD (using NAMs for derivation of new-generation Environmental Quality Standard; EQS).

3. Regulatory readiness

A major goal of WP5 is to improve the regulatory readiness of NAMs. Most of the assays listed in this document are still in the early stages of development. In line with the aforementioned goal, their readiness should increase in the remaining years of PARC. To ensure that this happens, the regulatory readiness of those assays will be evaluated at the beginning and at the end of the projects and the results will be presented in subsequent deliverables. Discussions are currently ongoing within WP5 (WPLs, TLs, PMs) regarding existing regulatory readiness assessment methods, which tool can cover the most specific features of the NAMs under WP5 and how to better adapt the tool to the actual needs (outcome expected in the first trimester of 2024).

Follow up actions on this activity include a readiness assessment (by method) to be conducted in 2024, dedicated strategies for selected NAM to increase their robustness by e.g. broadening the set of test chemicals and thus the applicability domain, contributing to AOPs, IATAs and respective case studies or inter lab transferability. This endeavour will be started in year 2025 of PARC and associated projects as well as potential follow ups as this issue will not be solved by PARC alone.

Although PARC will not perform full ring trials, it will contribute to validation as described in the position paper from WP5 & WP6 work package leaders and presented to the MB in November 2023 (See Annex II).

4. Methods

Assay information was collected using Excel tables and reviewed by the partners performing each assay and cross-checked with the twelve project descriptions in PARC WP5. The Excel table is based on the one used for AD5.3, including not only Task 5.2 but any NAMs across WP5.

As already explained in the previous section, our aim is to assess the methods at the beginning of the project in order to identify their weaknesses and to improve the readiness of the methods specifically there. At the end of the project, the same tool will be used to assess the method again and try to reduce it to a specific score so that the progress of the method can be presented in future deliverables.

5. Results

The main expected outputs that are considered to address the identified and stated regulatory needs are listed here by endpoint, while the most specific contributions from the individual assays are presented in Annex I with the list of NAMs under development.

Neurotoxicity:

- New NAMs that fill the current gaps in the DNT *in vitro* testing battery (IVB). Here, test methods will be set up from existing test systems (human stem cell-based systems, zebrafish).
- New NAMs for ANT. Current test systems will be used for test method set-up (human stem cell-based systems, zebrafish).

Metabolic endocrine disruption

- Assessment of an extended spectrum of substances for priority families, including major metabolites and breakdown molecules, allowing further Modes of Action (MoA) exploration, as well as adverse outcome pathway (AOP) and read-across development.
- Development of NAMs encompassing hepatic and non-hepatic *in vitro* systems including multi-tissue crosstalk, opening the road for a refined assessment of the obesogenic effects of MDC. It involves a deep mechanistic exploration of key cellular pathways using human *in vitro* models, as well as parallel additional 3R-compliant models and novel methods, including imagery.

Non genotoxic carcinogenicity

- Development of internationally acceptable *in vitro* testing batteries (NAMs) and IATAs.
- Evaluation of the reliability and relevance of the systems (sensitivity and specificity) and their complementarity in detecting different MoAs involved in non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, by testing a sufficiently large set of reference compounds, including those prioritized in PARC.
- Development and optimization of the more complex systems to allow a more physiological evaluation of activity for a subset of the reference compounds.

Endocrine Disruption - Thyroid

- Identification of upstream MIEs or KEs for downstream AOs relevant to the outcome of the endocrine disrupting effect.
- Target specific KEs for development of NAMs to increase the predictive power of non-animal test data for hazard identification and/or risk assessment.
- Investigate direct *versus* indirect perturbation of the TH axis by exogenous agents.
- To establish a novel developmental stem cell-based assay with human relevance.
- Characterise the evolutionary conservation of the THS axis to make better use of non-human NAMS (e.g. fish, invertebrates) to inform human health risks.
- Develop a robust IATA specific for THSD.

Immunotoxicity

- Delivery of a set of *in vitro* systems that allow the measurement of key events in the immune system function or dysfunction.
- Identify new or specific endpoints to explore better the immune system cellular content and activity, cytokine, antibody production and release, and the effect of signalling between different immune cells to develop relevant assays.
- Characterization of different primary cell systems and cell lines as well as epithelial and immune cell co-cultures.
- Characterization of key events in NAMs to support the build-up of AOPs and IATAs.

Environment

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- Investigation of the potential adverse effects (e.g., apical endpoints such as mortality, effects related to the anticipated mode of action or MIE, effects on reproduction, effects on endocrine system) of certain individual substances and “real-life” mixtures of BPA alternatives on non-mammalian organisms belonging to different taxa.
- Development of *in silico* and modelling tools for hazard assessment of BPA alternatives to ultimately support grouping of substances and read-across approaches based on NAMs.
- Development and advancing invertebrate models as NAMs for the hazard assessment of BPA alternatives and/or other prioritized chemicals.
- Development and advancing alternative 3R-compatible vertebrate aquatic model organisms for environmental hazard assessment of BPA alternatives and other prioritized chemicals.

6. Conclusion

This deliverable updated the list of test assays in use, planned to be used or developed in PARC WP5 (first list version in AD5.3). Focusing on WP5 Task 5.1 and 5.2, D5.1 also gathers the assay rationale, as well as the regulatory needs addressed by each assay. While overall contributing to a reduction or refinement in the use of animal tests aim at supporting the establishment of the causality between toxicant and hazard manifestation and identification of how the toxicity happens. This information will aid robust IATA development for the chosen (eco)toxicological endpoints. Although full replacement of animal tests is always desired, reduction and refinement are more realistic prospects within the timeframe of PARC. The detailed reasoning for NAMs is nicely explained in Hartung *et al.*, 2013 and NNAMs used in PARC WP5 in Marx-Stoelting *et al.*, 2023.

An important aspect of this deliverable and its elements is that it is a work in progress. The list of test assays will change since the development of test batteries in each WP5 project, as well as the interactions with AOP and IATA development will highlight if other Key Events may be deemed more critical which may require the addition of new methods and the possible abandonment of others.

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TG231 Amphibian Metamorphosis Assay

TG236 Fish Embryo Acute Toxicity (FET) Test

TG241 The Larval Amphibian Growth and Development Assay (LAGDA)

TG243 *Lymnaea stagnalis* Reproduction Test

TG248 *Xenopus* Eleutheroembryonic Thyroid Assay (XETA)

TG250 EASZY assay - Detection of Endocrine Active Substances, acting through estrogen receptors, using transgenic tg(cyp19a1b:GFP) Zebrafish embrYos

TG414 Prenatal Developmental Toxicity Study

TG421 Reproduction/Developmental Toxicity Screening Test

TG422 Combined Repeated Dose Toxicity Study with the Reproduction/Developmental Toxicity Screening Test

TG426 Developmental Neurotoxicity Study

TG443 Extended One-Generation Reproductive Toxicity Study

TG451 Carcinogenicity studies

TG453 Combined chronic toxicity/carcinogenicity studies

TG470 Mammalian erythrocyte pig-a gene mutation assay

TG474 Mammalian erythrocyte micronucleus test

TG475 Mammalian bone marrow chromosomal aberration test

TG488 Transgenic rodent somatic and germ cell gene mutation assays

Annex I

1. NAMs for human health assessment

The regulatory relevance for the test is described before the table since is similar among test that will be selected and grouped in test batteries, the subsections of the table highlight such possible grouping. In contract, in NAMs for Environmental Health, a column had been added to the table to specify the regulatory relevance per assay.

1.1 NAMs for DNT

Regulatory relevance:

- Using NAMs to screen cellular effects of BPA alternatives / Close knowledge gaps regarding BPA alt.
- Refining and building NAMs that cover gaps and demonstrate added value to the DNT *in vitro* test battery (IVB).
- This assay aims to fill the gaps regarding hippocampal development and plasticity. It implements the currently developed DNT tests, and particularly the *in vitro* cortical models for the cognitive/behavioural endpoint.

Partners List:

INRAE (FR): Catherine Viguié

CNRS (FR): Sakina Mhaouty-Kodja

LIH (LU): Nathalie Grova, Jonathan Turner

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>In vitro - Adverse cognitive effects</i>					
Hippocampal neurons for cognitive/ED test	Human	hiPSC-derived hippocampal neurons	2D	Human induced Pluripotent Stem Cells (hiPSC) will be used to generate human hippocampal neurons and (i) characterize the cellular effects of tested substances (e.g. dendrite development, synaptogenesis, spine density and neurogenesis, neuroplasticity) (CNRS). (ii) The molecular targets and relevant biomarkers will be identified using targeted and non-targeted approaches (RNA-seq, e.g. expression of estrogenic and thyroid hormone receptors and regulated signalling pathways including NMDA receptors, and kinases involved in neurotransmission) (CNRS and INRAE). (iii) In addition, DNA methylation will be analyzed (LIH) on selected target genes and the whole epigenome and compared with the transcriptomic data.	CNRS INRAE LIH

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Regulatory relevance:

To improve the DNT-IVB and build an ANT-IVB (adult neurotoxicity test battery), we focus on

- (i) human cells that avoid the problem of species specificity,
- (ii) zebrafish embryos, a low-cost screening tool with integrated nervous system functions that is an unprotected species before 5 days of life and therefore considered to be an alternative whole organism that can reveal neurotoxic effects on key missing endpoints such as learning and memory, and
- (iii) *in silico* approaches.

Partners List:

INSERM (FR): Patrick Babin, Anja Knoll-Gellida

UU (SE): Caroline Agrillo, Ola Spjuth (with Joëlle Rüegg as advisor)

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AIT (AT): Winfried Neuhaus, Andreas Brachner

NMBU (NO): Jan Ludvig Lyche, Erik Ropstad, Selma Hurem

UG-PL (PL): Karolina Jagiello, Beata Judzinska, Tomasz Puzyn

Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>Whole organism assays (In vivo)</i>			
Action 1: Fill existing gaps in the DNT-IVB			
1.2 Build NAMs that cover battery gaps			
Seizures. Electric field pulse motor response test (EFPMRT)	Zebrafish embryo	The electric field pulse motor response test (EFPMRT) enables direct stimulation of the motor system via the activation of reticulospinal neurons independently of sensory processing. Quantitative data relating to locomotor behavior after an EFP are collected by high-speed video capture and an automated analysis of the data. This NAM will capture chemicals that cause seizurogenic activity.	INSERM

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Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution
		Optimization of a high throughput tracking system to quantify locomotor deficit by comparison of control and chemical-treated groups of eleuthero-embryos after electrical stimulation.	
Thigmotaxis (Anxiety) Assay	Zebrafish embryos	Validation of a thigmotaxis assay for larval zebrafish (120 hpf) compatible with the use of a 96-well plate format and automated video recording technology. Thigmotaxis (wall-hugging behavior) has been widely used in mammalian models to study anxiety-related behaviors.	ISCIII
Zebrafish motor neuron toxicity and DNT persistence	Zebrafish (embryo and larvae)	Zebrafish motor neuron toxicity. Evaluation of motorfunction (motorneuron development, innervation of musculature) assessed by behavioural testing e.g. spontaneous tail coiling assay (24hpf), behaviour analysis at 5 dpf (L/D transition test) and microscopic examination of motorneuron development. Zebrafish DNT persistence. ZF embryo presents a valuable whole-organism model, capable of detecting DNT and/or ANT by mechanisms that require organ-interaction or metabolic activation. Light/Dark (L/D) transition test following chemical exposure from 0-4 days, testing on day 5 to identify DNT chemicals, and behavioural experiments used to study persistence of DNT effects at 5 dpf. Data will be used to discuss the place of the L/D transition test in a testing strategy for DNT. 1. Study the added value of TG model (NRP1-GFP) in locomotor assays for DNT assessment. 2. Investigate the persistence of effects observed in the Zebrafish embryo DNT protocol in adult fish.	RIVM
Learning and memory. Visual and acoustic motor response (VAMR) assay	Zebrafish embryos	This NAM adds missing endpoints to account for locomotion, startle response, learning, and memory (many of these are included in the rodent test guideline targeted for replacement - OECD 426). The Visual and Acoustic Motor Response (VAMR) NAM is performed in zebrafish embryos and: - Consists of a battery of 16 endpoints - Captures visual and acoustic startle response, visual motor response, habituation learning, potentiation of habituation, memory retention	UFZ

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>In vitro assays</i>					
Action 1: Fill existing gaps in the DNT-IVB					
1.1 Refine existing NAMs to reduce cost and increase throughput					

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Human Neuronal Network Formation hNNF Assay	Human	2D mixed neuron/glia cultures	2D	The hNNF assay is based on hiPSC-derived excitatory and inhibitory neurons, co-cultured with primary human astroglia (commercially available kit) and will be re-established with in-house generated cells. By testing a training set of DNT positive and negative compounds, as well as specific target compounds, the assay's readiness for regulatory application will be improved. Furthermore, the throughput of the assay will be increased. Details: - Use of human instead of rat primary cells. Re-establish and refine the protocol with in-house generated hiPSC-derived excitatory and inhibitory neurons to reduce costs.	IUF
Human synaptogenesis assay	Human	IMR90 hiPSC-derived human neural progenitor cells (hNPCs)	2D	The hNPC multicultures of neurons (glutamatergic, GABAergic, dopaminergic) and astrocytes will be treated with training/positive compounds based on a common list to refine existing gaps in the DNT IVB (replace the synaptogenesis assay based on rat cortical neurons in the current DNT IVB), where transcriptomics and protein markers for neurodevelopmental processes (and key events) may be used to develop AOPs. Details: - 96 well plates, hNPC derived from IMR90 hiPSC. Current DNT IVB assay based on rat cortical cells (US-EPA) -Test method available for (human) synaptogenesis considering astrocyte contribution and species to replace the synaptogenesis assay based on rat cortical neurons in the current DNT IVB.	NIPH
Automated HT cellular neurotoxicity assay for fast screening of chemicals and sample extracts (complex mixtures)	Human	SH-SY5Y	2D	Additional Endpoints Increase likelihood of detecting mitochondrial toxicants: - Mitotox variants UKN 2, 4, 5 - Neural crest cell migration (UKN2) * - Neurite outgrowth of human dopaminergic neurons (UKN4) ** - Human immature peripheral neurons (UKN5) *** - Mitotox + neurite outgrowth, ultra HTP (UFZ) Automated HT cellular neurotoxicity assay with endpoints of cytotoxicity, neurite outgrowth inhibition, mitochondrial toxicity and (not multiplexed but under the same conditions) ACHE inhibition.	UFZ UKON

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
*UKN2 / cMINC (circular migration inhibition of neural crest cells)	Human	hiPSC-derived human neural crest cells (NCCs)	2D	The assay assesses disturbances of NCC migration during foetal development. The number of migrated NCC, as well as cell viability are measured simultaneously using high content imaging. Thereby the processes of cell migration and cell death are measured in cells exposed to potential toxicants for 24 h. The data of this method are meant to predict developmental disorders and malformations e.g., neural tube defects or craniofacial malformations caused by compound exposure during foetal development. This assay can also be performed under conditions that allow the detection of mitochondrial toxicity that is often missed in the standard assay	UKON
**UKN4 / NeuriTox test	Human	human neurons (LUHMES cells) at a stage of neurite growth	2D	The assay assesses (a) disturbances in the development of the nervous system/brain structures, and (b) direct damage to the adult nervous system, by exposure to toxicants. The neurite area (which serves as indirect measurement of neuronal interconnectivity) of stained differentiating neurons as well as cellular viability are measured simultaneously using high content imaging. The processes of neurite outgrowth and cell viability are assessed. This assay can also be performed under conditions that allow the detection of mitochondrial toxicity that is often missed in the standard assay	UKON
***UKN5 / PeriTox test	Human	hiPSC-derived human immature dorsal root ganglia neurons	2D	It assesses (a) disturbances in the development of the (peripheral) nervous system, and (b) direct damage of the peripheral nervous system, by exposure to toxicants. The neurite area (which serves as an indirect measurement of neuronal interconnectivity) of stained differentiating neurons, as well as cellular viability are measured simultaneously using high content imaging. The processes of neurite outgrowth and cell death are measured. This assay can also be performed under conditions that allow the detection of mitochondrial toxicity that is often missed in the standard assay.	UKON

1.2 Build NAMs that cover battery gaps

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Neuronal Tube Closure UKN1 / rosette formation assay (RoFA)	Human	human iPS cells differentiating to neuroectodermal cells/neural stem cells	2D	It assesses (a) disturbances in the early phase of neural induction and can be used in an alternative setup to detect disturbances (b) in the process of self-organization to neural rosettes (reflecting formation of the neural tube <i>in vitro</i>). Cells self-organize into neural rosettes after 12 days of differentiation. Cells are exposed to compounds from d0-d4 during neural induction. The number of rosettes and nuclei are assessed by using high content imaging.	UKON
1.3 Build confidence that NAMs cover key modes of action (ED, epigenomic)					
Epigenomic changes as early markers for DNT	Human (potentially also zebrafish)	Decision on which <i>in vitro</i> DNT models to be assessed is in process	To be determined	Epigenomic (DNA methylation) analyses will be performed in selected models treated with positive and negative compounds. Two methods (Illumina EPIC bead array and GBS-MeDIP) with different resolution and price will be compared to assess if cheaper methods with less resolution will give sufficient information to result in added value and allow to compare with human data.	UU
Action 2: Assemble an ANT – IVB 1.0 focused on acute receptor-mediated effects					
2.1: Cellular NAMs					
Blood-brain barrier / Development of a human stem cell-based assay on Acute NeuroToxicity	Human	human brain capillary endothelial like cells derived from IMR90-4 human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSC)	2D - Transwell	The assay determines the influence of chemicals on the functionality of the blood-brain barrier. Main parameters to be measured for the integrity of the barrier is the transendothelial electrical resistance and permeability of a paracellular marker. In addition, cell viability and molecular changes (in particular epigenetic changes such as DNA-methylation) are planned to be measured.	AIT

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Peripheral myelin toxicity Development of a human stem cell-based assay on myelin toxicity influencing peripheral sensory and motor functions.	Human	human neural progenitor cells (hNPCs) derived from IMR90 human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSC)	2D and 3D	Development of a human stem cell-based assay on myelin toxicity influencing peripheral sensory and motor functions. Sensory or motor neurons will be co-cultured with Schwann cells in 1) 3D spheres and 2) in 2D co-culture, to identify the most favourable setup for high-throughput testing. After 4-8 weeks in culture cell types as well as myelin formation will be analysed by RT-qPCR and immunocytochemistry followed by automated myelin quantification.	TiHo
hMNR Human multi-neurotransmitter receptor / BrainSphere assay	Human	hiPSC-derived mixed neuron/glia cultures	3D	3D hiPSC-derived BrainSpheres include different neuronal subtypes. Treating the cells with neurotransmitter agonists and antagonists and measuring the spontaneous electrical activity (Spike Sorting), will allow the detection of specific compound effects on each neuronal subtype.	IUF

1.2 Metabolic Endocrine Disruption

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Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>Whole organism assays (In vivo)</i>			
Development of early life stage (embryo, larval) zebrafish metabolic disruption assay	Zebrafish	A method that uses zebrafish larvae will be developed, since they are feeding and thus toxicant exposure can be combined with experimental diets. A custom western diet (high in fat, carbohydrates and cholesterol) was developed for this purpose. It will be explored to which extent metabolic disruption can already be detected in zebrafish embryos that are not yet exogenously feeding and are thus considered an alternative to animal testing. Examples of endpoints include yolk size, oxidative stress, and transcript levels of genes related to lipid metabolism.	UAntwerpen

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>In vitro</i> assays					
<i>In vitro</i> assays for screening Metabolic Disruption (MBD)					
<i>In vitro</i> test battery to analyze mTOR modulation by test chemicals	Human	Hepa RG		Hub of surrogate markers for the detection of obesogenic compounds. In this activity, <i>in vitro</i> assays will be developed to detect compounds that disrupt metabolic signaling to MTOR. MTOR activity will be addressed by quantitative high resolution mass spectrometry (HR-MS) and immune assays.	UIBK
Screening assay for phospholipidosis in liver cells (lipid metabolism)	Human	HepaRG	2D	This assay will be developed as a high throughput assay to characterise and identify MDCs that are causing phospholipidosis in hepatocytes. As a follow up, the molecular mechanism of these potent MDCs will be analysed to understand the MoA and to fill data gaps in the AOP for phospholipidosis. Multi-omics approaches including transcriptomics and proteomics will be used	BfR
Test system for pancreatic beta cell signaling and function disruption by MDCs.	Human	Endoc- β H1, Endoc- β H5	2D	Omics analyses of gene and protein expression to elucidate the specific pathways and processes that are disrupted by MDCs by means of bioinformatics data mining.	BfR
Development and optimization of adipocyte models to study adipocyte differentiation and response to test chemicals. (Part I from II)	Human	hMSCs	2D/3D serum free conditions	a) Assessment time/concentration-dependent effects of BPA alternatives on adipocyte differentiation in male and female primary human mesenchymal stem cell (hMSCs). We will explore different assay techniques (2D vs 3D, and serum free conditions). We will assess adipogenesis by high content imaging to enhance lipid accumulation readouts a in more quantitative manner.	IRAS-UU

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Development and optimization of adipocyte models to study adipocyte differentiation and response to test chemicals. (Part II from II)	Human		3D	b) Study the effects on adipokine and cytokine release, such as leptin, adiponectin and IL-6, in primary as well as co-cultures with macrophages and an induced inflamed state with lipopolysaccharide. Mechanisms of action determination will be established with transcriptomics read-outs for a limited set of exposures.	IRAS-UU
Unravel the Molecular principles of metabolic disruption using omics approaches	Human	Human SGBS cells	2D	Characterization of the molecular effects of BPA alternatives during adipogenesis using LC-MS/MS-based proteomics approaches to unravel the mode of action, identify relevant signaling pathways and decipher the responsible chemical-protein interaction network, defining die principles of metabolic disruption.	UFZ
Assessment of MDC effect on cultured primary human hepatocytes and human iPSC	Human	Cultured primary human hepatocytes and human iPSC		The readouts will be: -RNAseq to obtain genome wide expression profiles -An assay to quantify fluorophore coupled transporter assays to analyze the influence on import and secretion capacity -An assay to quantify triglycerides and lipid droplets to evaluate compromised lipid metabolism.	IfADo

1.3 Non-Genotoxic Carcinogenicity

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Partners List:

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 RIVM (NL): Mirjam Luijten, Harm Heusinkveld
 UKL (DE): Jörg Fahrer
 NILU (NO): Naouale El Yamani
 MU (CZ): Pavel Babica* (*Voluntary collaboration with WP5, no PM)

Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Whole organism assays (In vivo)			
Whole organism test model for oxidative stress	Zebrafish	The assay aims at measuring and localizing (organ level) oxidative stress responses in zebrafish embryos as a result of chemical exposure	RIVM

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
In vitro assays					

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Assessment of adhesion and migration properties of MCF-7 tumor cells in the presence of cells mimicking their microenvironment (hMADS) and various types of pollutants	Human	MCF-7 (human mammary tumoral cells)	2D	The assay measures the impedance (converted as a Cell index) of an electrode on which the MCF-7 cells are seeded allowing live measurements of potential phenotypical changes due to migration of the cells or changes in adhesion	INSERM
gH2AX/pH3 assay for the determination of the genotoxicity mode of action	Human	Multicellular liver spheroid/ HepaRG	2D and 3D	The gH2AX/pH3 assay will be developed in a high-throughput format to allow the identification in a cost-efficient screening platform for NGTxC potential of a chemical as well as to characterize molecular mechanisms. NOTE: To distinguish genotoxic from non-genotoxic carcinogenicity we need to test for genotoxic activity in parallel. In addition, we cannot rule out that a genotoxic activity might not be detected by the current standard tests. Thus, additional new gents assays might be useful to cover both aspects.	INRAE
Phenotypic Screening for breast cancer markers of carcinogenicity	Human	MCF7, HME1	2D	The assay will be developed in a high-throughput format to allow the identification of phenotypic changes characteristic for distinct MoA with an emphasis on EMT. As a follow up these markers will be further analysed to establish a cost-efficient screening platform for NGTxC as well as to characterize molecular mechanisms	BfR
Assessment of gap junctional intercellular communication by multiparametric scrape-loading dye transfer (mSL-DT) assay	Rodent (Fisher 344 rat)	WB-F344 (rat liver epithelial/oval cells)	2D	The assay measures levels of gap junctional intercellular communication (GJIC) mediated through connexin proteins, a physiological process whose inhibition has been linked to mitogenic signalling and other tumour promoting mechanisms activated by non-genotoxic carcinogens. The process has been identified as a key event in non-genotoxic carcinogenesis in the IATA proposed by the OECD expert group (Jacobs <i>et al.</i> 2020).	MU

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Standard and enzyme-modified alkaline comet assay for the detection of DNA strand breaks, alkali-labile sites and, oxidized and alkylated bases	Human	HepG2	2D and 3D	The standard alkaline comet assay detects single and double DNA strand breaks and alkali-labile site (ALS) at a single cell level. DNA breaks relax the supercoiled DNA of the nucleoids and the DNA is able to migrate toward the anode during an electrophoresis. ALS are converted into breaks due to the alkaline conditions used. The combination of the assay with the enzymes formamidopyrimidine DNA glycosylase (Fpg) or alkyladenine DNA glycosylase (hAAG) allows the detection of oxidized and alkylated bases, respectively, due to the introduction of breaks at the site of the corresponding lesion.	UNAV
Assessment of cell viability (MTS assay), proliferation (Ki67 marker), cell cycle analysis, genotoxic effects (gH2AX, histone H3), expression of targeted genes involved in DNA damage response, oxidative stress and epigenetic markers	Human	HepG2	3D	The MTS assay is a colorimetric method for the sensitive quantification of viable cells. It can assess cell proliferation, cell viability and cytotoxicity. Ki67 marker is expressed only in dividing cells therefore it is a marker of cell proliferation. gH2AX method detects DNA double strand breaks (clastogens), while histone H3-positive cells represent mitotic index (aneugens). The expression of targeted genes (toxicogenomic approach) will enable prediction, which pathways and corresponding genes are involved in the mode of action (MoA).	NIB

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Human iPSC reporters for adaptive stress response activation, cell cycle distribution, and mitogenic signalling	Human	induced pluripotent stem cells and derived lineages (focus: liver and mammary gland)	2D and 3D	The iPSC reporters allow analysis of pivotal key events in the proposed IATA of non-genotoxic carcinogens (Jacobs <i>et al.</i> 2020): oxidative stress, inflammatory signalling and mitogenic signalling. Using validation sets of chemical compounds with known toxic effects, the reporter lines will be evaluated with high content live cell confocal imaging for sensitivity and specificity in the detection of specific types of stress-response in different target organ lineages, in 2D or 3D. Since the mammary gland and the liver are two of the most prominent cancer target tissues in the NTP 2-year bioassay (Sistare <i>et al.</i> 2011), we will include iPSC-based progenitor cells of mammary epithelial cells and liver hepatocytes. These imaging-based approaches will be complemented by high throughput targeted mRNA sequencing using TempO-Seq (https://www.biospyder.com), as well as high throughput single-cell sequencing using BART-seq (Uzbas <i>et al.</i> 2019), to get broader insight in AOP activation and thresholds of carcinogenic events.	UL-LACDR
MCF7 reporters for pro-proliferative ER α signalling	Human	MCF7	2D	The MCF7 cell reporter lines allow single cell level measurements of the time-resolved activation of pro-proliferative ER α signalling.	UL-LACDR
Assessment of cell viability (Alamar Blue assay), proliferation (EdU incorporation), genotoxicity (γ H2AX), oxidative stress (CM-H2DCFDA), migration (wound healing assay) and EMT/morphology (Phalloidin/E-Cadherin)	Human	human colonic epithelial cells (HCEC) and HCT116 CRC cells	2D	The Alamar Blue assay is a sensitive fluorescent and colorimetric assay to assess cell viability and cytotoxicity. The EdU incorporation assay is a readout for DNA replication and thus cell proliferation. γ H2AX is a sensitive DNA damage marker. CM-H2DCFDA is a probe for reactive oxygen species. The wound healing assay monitors migration of cells as gap closure. Phalloidin stains the actin cytoskeleton, which is remodelled during EMT. E-Cadherin is an epithelial cell marker, which disappears during EMT in favour of mesenchymal markers.	UKL

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Assessment of cell viability (AlamarBlue assay), cell proliferation (relative growth activity), oxidative stress (H2DCFDA assay), inflammation (ELISA)	Human	JIMT-1	2D and 3D	3D breast cancer model (mammospheres/mammoaggregates) from JIMT-1 and comparison with response in 2D cultures. Several endpoints relevant for NGTxC will be investigated.	NILU

Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>In silico</i> assays			
Carcinogenicity model (CAESAR) (version 2.1.10)	Male or female rats	This model is based on Counter Propagation Neural Network CP ANN; The dependent variable is cancerogenic effect on rat, as binary classification: 0 (non-carcinogen), 1 (carcinogen)	IRFM
Carcinogenicity model (ISS) (version 1.0.3)	Human	The Carcinogenicity ISS model (version 1.0.3) is an implementation in VEGA software of the set of rules for carcinogenicity obtained from a decisional tree implemented in the ToxTree software	IRFM
Carcinogenicity oral classification model (IRFMN) (version 1.0.1)	Different species (Human, rat, mouse)	Classification and regression trees (CART)	IRFM
Carcinogenicity oral Slope Factor model (IRFMN) (version 1.0.1)	Different species (Human, rat, mouse)	Multi-layer perceptron – artificial neural networks (MLP-ANNs)	IRFM

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Carcinogenicity inhalation classification model (IRFMN) (version 1.0.1)	Different species (Human, rat, mouse)	Classification and regression trees (CART)	IRFM
Carcinogenicity inhalation Slope Factor model (IRFMN) (version 1.0.1)	Different species (Human, rat, mouse)	Multi-layer perceptron – artificial neural networks (MLP-ANNs)	IRFM

1.4 ED TH disruption

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Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Whole organism assays (In vivo)			
Whole organism model: zebrafish larvae and embryo & In vivo rat study: optimization and characterization of assays to identify Molecular Initiation Events (MIE)			
Zebrafish embryo assay with endpoints for thyroid hormone system disruption	Zebrafish (embryo)	Case study on AOP network-based cross-species comparison of thyroid hormone system disruption data in zebrafish and mammals to advance the use of a zebrafish embryo assay for informing on human health. The case study is based on data from the literature and generated in PARC.	UAntwerpen
Zebrafish embryo assays	Zebrafish (embryos and larvae up to 120 hpf)	Study of MIE: Thyroid Hormone transporters inhibition, Iodide transport (NIS) inhibition, Iodide accumulation. Study of hormonal KE: TSH, T3 and T4 levels. Study of thyroid gene expression. Study of morphological KE: swimbladder inflation, head and eye sizes. Study of behavioural KE: spontaneous tail coiling (24 hpf), visual locomotor response, thigmotaxis (anxiety), habituation to acoustic startle (non-associative learning). Compounds to be used include positive controls: Silycristin, ClO ₄ , MMI or PTU; and negative controls: DMSO, Tryptophan.	ISCI

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>In vitro</i> assays					
Optimization and characterization of assays to develop more extensive test batteries of NAMs that cover a broader range of Key Events (KEs) i.e. from Molecular Initiation Events (MIE) to Adverse Outcomes (AO); gaining more mechanistic knowledge on THSD for targeted NAM development					
Screening assays for TH-disruption for early-phase liver developmental toxicity	Human	Skin stem cell-derived hepatic cells	2D	Human skin-derived precursor cells (hSKP) acquire key properties of hepatic progenitor cells (hSKP-HPC) upon sequential exposure to hepatogenic growth factors and cytokines. They will be exploited to predict toxicity hazards due to non-classical THSDs during the early phases of liver development. The human <i>in vitro</i> data and the rat <i>in vivo</i> data, generated by DTU, will be combined to understand species differences and the relation between <i>in vivo</i> and <i>in vitro</i> data.	VUB
<i>In vitro</i> thyroid follicle model for identification of TH biosynthesis disruption	Porcine, (human)	Primary thyroid tissue	3D	The <i>in vitro</i> model will be established following current literature with potential adaptation to the porcine cell source and TH ELISA as integrative read-out of TH biosynthesis activity. This model will be challenged with compounds identified to interfere with Thyroid-related MIE by respective, MoA-focused methods.	BfR
<i>In vitro</i> overexpressing cell lines for thyroid hormone transporters OATP1C1 and OAT4	Human transporters	CHO (OATP1C1) and MDCK (OAT4)	2D	Cell lines overexpressing OATP1C1 or OAT4 are established and exposed simultaneously to thyroid hormone T4 and test compounds. Transporter inhibition is determined as a decreased T4 content in cell lysate.	VUA
Integrated model for measuring thyroid hormone transport inhibition across the blood-cerebrospinal fluid barrier	Human	iPSC	3D	An <i>in vitro</i> organoid model will be established, based on current literature, to determine the transport of thyroid hormone across choroid plexus epithelial cells into vesicles containing a secretion with very high similarity to cerebrospinal fluid.	VUA

DELIVERABLE D5.1

<p><i>In vitro</i> assays to identify inhibitors of thyroperoxidase, deiodinase type 1,2,3 and dehalogenase as potentially relevant MIE of TH prereceptor control.</p>	<p>Human transporters</p>	<p>Human, recombinant enzyme</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>The methods are used to identify chemicals/compounds that interfere with the given enzymes, therefore being potential EDs. These <i>in vitro</i> assays will be applied to identify/characterize compound upon testing in a more complex <i>in vitro</i> method. Furthermore, they can be used to extend QSAR training sets and to test their predictivity.</p>	<p>BfR</p>
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Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<p><i>In chemico</i> assays</p>				
<p><i>In chemico</i> assays to quantify deiodinase type 1 and dehalogenase activities as potentially relevant endpoints/read-outs in animal studies</p>	<p>Mouse, rat, human, mule, sheep (any species with respective activities)</p>	<p>Tissue homogenate</p>	<p>These read outs might serve as a) indicators of changes in intracellular TH availability or b) might indicate a specific interference with the respective enzymes by e.g., environmental chemicals in (toxicological) animal studies.</p>	<p>BfR</p>

1.5 Immunotoxicity

Regulatory relevance:

- To develop a NAM for the testing of immunomodulating potential of inhaled chemicals, including mycotoxins from *Alternaria*. The data generated using this new NAM can be envisioned as a component in a larger assay battery with different toxicological endpoints to support risk assessment and the establishment of OELs for *Alternaria* toxins. If successful, this NAM may also be used to test for inhalation immune-modulating effects of other chemicals of concern.
- Identification of novel and universal endpoints for assessing immunomodulatory properties of mycotoxins by systematically testing a broad spectrum of mycotoxins using cutting-edge analytical techniques.
- To increase mechanistic knowledge about the immunotoxic effects of *Alternaria* toxins by filling data gaps regarding the immunomodulatory role of the mycotoxins via toll like receptors and Dectin receptors.

Partners List:

STAMI (NO): Steen Mollerup, Solveig Krapf, Anne Straumfors

NIPH (NO): Hubert Dirven, Nicola Margareta Smith, Igor Snapkow

NVI (NO): Anita Solhaug, Christiane Kruse Fæste, Gunnar Eriksen Sundstøl, Lada Ivanova

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>In vitro assays</i>					
<i>1- Respiratory immunotoxicity</i>					
Inhalation: Immunotoxic effects in 3D inhalation model (e.g. EpiAirway), including transcriptomics and epigenomics	Human	-Human derived primary tracheal/bronchial epithelial cells (TBE), -THP-1 monocyte cell line, -HMEC-1 fibroblast cell line.	3D co-culture	The human 3D mucociliary lung tissue model (EpiAirway™) will be used for pulmonary toxicity assessment of <i>Alternaria</i> toxins. The co-cultures will be exposed with single and mixtures of toxins (with or without co-exposure to LPS) before collecting the cells for transcriptomics analysis. Pathway analysis with a particular focus on pulmonary immunotoxicity will be carried out. This study aims to develop a NAM for the testing of immunomodulating potential of inhaled chemicals, including mycotoxins from <i>Alternaria</i>	STAMI (Alternaria toxins)
<i>2- Immunosuppression, including response to vaccination</i>					

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Systemically: Immunosuppression of enniatins and <i>Alternaria</i> toxins <i>in vitro</i> in human blood cells	Human	Volunteer human donors isolated peripheral blood mononuclear cells PBMCs	2D	Initially, human primary PBMCs will be subjected to a series of concentrations of toxins, and the cytotoxicity/viability will be assessed to establish operational concentrations. Subsequently, the release of various cytokines will be quantified using a multiplex assay (established panel), and the exposed cells will be extensively profiled using mass cytometry (panel will be developed based on the results of previously named experiments).	NIPH (enniatis, Alternaria Toxins)
3- Others, Immunotoxic effects Dectin reporter & Gut					
TLR and Dectin reporter assays (HEK293)	Human	HEK293 human embryo kidney cell line	Monolayer	Immunomodulating potential of the Alternaria mycotoxins on Nf-kB activation via toll like receptors (TLR2 and TLR4) and the Dectin receptors 1a and 1b signalling will be explored, using HEK-Blue™ reporter cell assays. The reporter cell assays will be exposed to mycotoxins in combination with natural activators of these receptors.	STAMI (Alternaria toxins)

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Gut: Immunotoxic effects in 3D tissue model of the human small intestine	Human	Primary human small intestinal epithelial cells (HSIE)	Cultivated on inserts	3D tissue model of a human small intestine, highly differentiated and with a fibroblast layer enabling immune responses and metabolism studies (EpiIntestinal 3D <i>in vitro</i> Microtissues MatTek Life Sciences)	NVI (Alternaria toxins)

Regulatory relevance:

While no OECD test guidelines are available to fill data gaps of BPA alternatives for immunotoxicity, only scientifically relevant methods will be used in accordance with the OECD Detailed Review Paper on *In Vitro* Test Addressing Immunotoxicity with a Focus on Immunosuppression (Series on Testing and Assessment No. 360). For all methods used, SOPs will be defined to ensure transferability and reproducibility.

Partners List:

MUI (AT): Johanna Gostner

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UL FFA (SI): Marija Sollner Dolenc, Nina Franko

ISS (IT): Simonetta Pallesch

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>In vitro</i> assays					
Immunosuppression					
Investigation of the relationship between bisphenols immunotoxicity and their effect on the inflammation-induced tryptophan breakdown and related immunobiochemical pathways.	Human	human PBMC and/or relevant human monocyte-derived cell lines	2D	Immunometabolic markers produced by human PBMC and/or relevant human monocyte-derived cell lines will be measured together with standard proliferation assays to generate information on cytotoxicity and cell viability.	MUI
Identification of immune cell targets and effects of bisphenols on immune functions	Human	human derived peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC)	2D	The impact on antigen presenting cell functions (e.g., surface marker upregulation, cytokine production), T cells polarization (e.g., Th1, Th2, Th17, Treg), NK (Natural Killer) cell activity, cytokine and immunoglobulin production will be investigated using human derived peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) purified for buffy coats obtained from healthy male and female donors. Gender differences and interindividual variability are evaluated.	UMIL
Effects of BPA substitutes on T-cell activation	Human	Jurkat, THP-1, LCL	suspension	Effects of selected bisphenols on T-cell activation are being investigated using Jurkat cell. In the later stages of the project, effects on THP-1 cells can be investigated as well as on B cells (LCL). Intra-individual variability can be assessed using LCL. Coculture will be prepared using THP-1 and Jurkat cell lines.	UL FFA

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>In silico</i> assay				
Investigation of the relationship between bisphenols immunotoxicity and their effect on the glucocorticoid system.	Human	luciferase reporter cell line MDA-kb2 (for GR activity study)	<i>In silico</i> screening of the selected BPA alternatives by WP5 and additionally other BPA analogues will be performed. For bisphenols with hits from <i>in silico</i> screening, their immunotoxic potential will be investigated using human immune cell lines, as well as their interactions with the glucocorticoid receptor (GR), For the GR activity, the luciferase reporter cell line MDA-kb2 will be used, and agonism/antagonism on GR determined.	UL FFA

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DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>In vitro</i> assays					
Respiratory immunotoxicity and sensitization: identification of respiratory sensitizers					
Bronchial air-liquid interface (ALI) model alone or in combination with monocytes (co-culture)	Human	bronchial epithelial cell lines (e.g., Beas2B) differentiated at ALI in cocultures with monocytic cell lines (e.g., THP-1)	3D	Air liquid interface (ALI)-cultures of differentiated bronchial epithelial cell lines grown on inserts will be used alone or in combination with monocytic cells (cell lines) located in the bottom compartment of the coculture. THP-1 cells can be differentiated to macrophage-like or dendritic cell-like phenotypes. These cell models can be used to assess different endpoints and will be used to assess the effects of respiratory sensitizers.	MUI
Development of NAMs by screening dendritic cell (DC) activation by sensitized lung epithelial cells or by the extracellular vesicles derived from them	Human	human bronchial epithelial cell-line and primary dendritic cells	2D	A human airway epithelial cell line (AEC) will be treated with a proven respiratory sensitizer. Extracellular vesicles (EVs) will be isolated from the supernatant of treated AECs. The effect of these EVs on DC will be evaluated and compared to the effects of the treated AECs on DCs. DC activation will be evaluated by molecular and cellular assays. Results will be validated in an <i>ex vivo</i> model using the broncho-alveolar lavage fluid of sensitized mice. The content of EVs will be analysed by various omics methods to screen for sensitization markers.	NPHC
Bronchial air-liquid interface (ALI) model (monoculture)	Human	Bronchial epithelial cell line (Calu-3)	3D	The model has as advantage that upon culture at the air, the monolayer is maintained for at least 4 weeks, retaining a high Transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER). Upon prolonged culture at the air, Calu-3 cells develop villi. Amenable for chemical exposure, infection, or combined chemical exposure/infection experiments. Parameters to test: viability (WST-1 and LDH), barrier function (TEER), cytokine/chemokine release (e.g., IL-6, IL-8), tight junction presence (ZO-1 staining).	RIVM

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Bronchial air-liquid interface (ALI) model with macrophages (co-culture)	Human	Bronchial epithelial cell line (Calu-3); macrophages are differentiated either from primary monocytes or the monocytic cell line THP-1.	3D	Compared to the monoculture model, the co-culture model also comprises macrophages, making it especially suitable for experiments on (nano)particles and fibers. Additional cytokines/chemokines produced by macrophages, can be added to the test panel.	RIVM
ALIsens: Assay to identify the hazard of chemicals to induce respiratory sensitization	Human	Human cell lines	3D	The model is composed of multiple cell lines seeded on opposite sides of a multi-porous membrane. The model is capable to discriminate respiratory irritants and sensitizers. The actual differentiation is based on surface markers, chemokines and gene expression.	LIST
Immunosuppression, including response to vaccination: determine common markers of immunosuppression and response to vaccination and identify the most relevant <i>in vitro</i> or <i>ex vivo</i> system relevant to human health.					
25-multiparameter flow cytometry immunoassay for characterization of immune cell populations	Human	PBMCs	2D	With this assay immune cell populations can be further characterized using a 25-multiparameter flow cytometry method. It will be used to investigate chemical-mediated effects on PBMCs by describing both surface and intracellular markers at cellular level. This assay will be also used for Immunostimulation - inflammation	UFZ

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
<i>In vitro</i> substitution for Whole Blood Cytokine Release Assay	Human	Jurkat, THP-1, LCL	3D Suspension	Following the application of known immunosuppressants the changes in secreted cytokines will be investigated. A panel of cytokines that change independently of the immunosuppressive mechanism will be selected as markers for immunosuppression. In the more advanced stages of the project, the lymphoblastoid cell line LCL will be added to the co-culture (prepared with THP-1 and Jurkat cell lines) to bring the model closer to whole blood. Moreover, as commonly used Jurkat T cells have a mutation in glucocorticoid receptor, we will also use a GR-GAL4 Luciferase Reporter Jurkat Cell Line in order to investigate whether T-cell inhibition is mediated via glucocorticoid receptor or not. Other mechanisms underlying immunosuppression will be examined on THP-1 and Jurkat cell line to exploit the effects on signaling pathways.	UL FFA
Assay to screen for effects on B cells	Human	Namalwa B cell line	Suspension	The human Namalwa B cell line are B lymphocytes isolated from a 3-year-old patient with Burkitt's lymphoma. According to Van Belle et al. 2016 the Namalwa B cell line is considered a relevant model to study effect of B lymphocyte immunosuppressants. The Namalwa B cell line will be used to effects of model immunosuppressant and priority chemicals using whole genome gene expression profiling (RNA seq). The aim is to identify biomarkers that are likely key events in pathways relevant for adverse effects on immune cells. These biomarkers will be used for the further development of NAMs to screen compounds for immunotoxicity.	WR

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
Screening assays for Natural Killer cells immunotoxicity - apply to a context of early-life exposure	Human	CD34+ Hematopoietic Stem Cells (NK derived iPSC)	2D suspension	Early life environment is increasingly recognized as a crucial factor that deeply influences health and wellbeing later in life. This period plays a primordial role in determining the lifelong trajectory and health of the immune system, particularly NK cells. Natural killer cells are the founding members of the innate lymphoid cell (ILC) family that are both natural cytotoxic and have antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity. The relevance of our human <i>in vitro</i> model will be checked on a early environmental <i>in vivo</i> model on a selection of bisphenol analogues of high concern.	LIH
Using PBMCs to assess immunosuppression using PFAS - a tiered approach	Human	PBMCs	2D	Three tiers of testing I) cell viability II) luminex multiplex assay for cytokine quantification III) CyTOF for immunophenotyping	NIPH
Response to vaccination assay	Human	PBMCs or established cell lines (THP1, Jurkat)	2D suspension	In this assay, immune cell population and related secreted cytokines will be investigated after challenge to antigen.	INSERM
Immunostimulation – inflammation: Detection of proinflammatory potential of endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDC)					

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Cell type	Cell format	Short description	Contributing partner institution
NAM to determine metabolically-induced chronic inflammatory disease via oral exposure	human	Adipocytes differentiated from mesenchymal stem cells, intestinal epithelial cells (Caco-2, HT29MTX, organoids), immune cells (monocytes, macrophages, DC)	3D	The proposed NAM combines intestinal epithelial cells with adipocytes and immune cells to assess effects of EDC in KE related to inflammatory diseases EDC-induced metabolic syndrome, resulting in inflammatory diseases such as T2D, etc. The main route of exposure is via GALT (gut-associated lymphoid tissue) which results in possibly hazardous insults on gut epithelial cells, which are in connection with visceral adipose tissue and immune cells (mainly macrophages and innate T cells). See Villeneuve et al, Toxicol Sci. 163:346-352, 2018: with mentioning of 3 central hub-KE for inflammation: KE1=cell stress; KE2=release of proinflammatory mediators; KE3-migration and activation of immune cells.	UU-IRAS
Barrier immunity: Facilitation of regulatory evaluation of potential health-hazard and risk assessment, based on relevant epithelial cell stress, toxicity data and also concerning the broader effect of the substances on tissue microenvironmental interplays and local inflammatory response.					
Screening assays for bisphenol-induced changes in epithelial-stromal cells interplay.	Human / mouse	Polarized intestinal or lung epithelial cancer cell lines, fibroblast and monocytic cell lines	3D	Co-cultures of polarized intestinal or lung epithelial cells with a mixture of fibroblasts and macrophages (differentiated from THP1 cells into stages M0, M1, or M2) will be exposed to relevant concentrations of bisphenols. The impact of the chemicals on the secretome of epithelial and stroma cells will be analysed using cytokine arrays and/or unbiased mass spec analysis. Focus will be placed on cellular stress indicators (ROS production, ER stress via detection of phosphorylated eIF2 α -S51, p38 MAPK-T180/182 and AMPK-T172), as well as on changes in macrophage differentiation (RT-PCR of M1 and M2 markers).	INSA

2. NAMs for environmental toxicity assessment

Partners List:

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DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Whole organism assays (In vivo)				
Neurotoxicity				
Fish embryo test with automated morphology and behaviour assessment (stages up to 5 days post fertilisation are considered as NAM and are 3R compliant)	Zebrafish (embryo, <i>Danio rerio</i>)	Zebrafish embryos are exposed to test chemicals or extracts from environmental sample. The exposure period can vary depending on the research question and whether developmental or acute interaction is targeted. The assay is partially automatised using image and video analysis for morphology analysis and video tracking for behaviour assessment. The behaviour assays are further developed towards improving the capacity for identification of acute and developmental neurotoxicity. Morphological analysis aims at providing patterns of diagnostic information and support specific analysis of effects. Regarding the regulatory perspective we intent to provide a screening opportunity for neuroactive compounds, for which test systems are lacking. Further our patterns of multiple endpoints would be useful for read across between chemicals.	UFZ	To provide a comprehensive assessment of chemical effects. Cellular assays often focus on very specific mechanisms and therefore a battery of assays is required. The zebrafish embryo, as a complex (but still alternative) organismic model, can address many endpoints. There is a particular focus on complementing cellular assays for neurotoxicity and providing pattern of action analysis that helps to assess specificity for particular effects that are assessed, for example, by endpoints in cellular models or transgenic reporter systems. It also allows read across between chemicals, e.g., for BPA analogues and surrogates, to fill the gap of many untested chemicals.
Zebrafish neurotoxicity recovery assays	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Zebrafish embryos are exposed to chemicals for a period of 6 days and are subsequently placed in chemical-free medium to allow recovery of chemical effects. During the exposure and recovery phase behaviour assays, structural analysis of neurons and muscles, transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics are performed. The goal of this assay is to understand molecular mechanisms underlying transient and persistent neurotoxic effects with the aim to identify molecular markers for predicting the longevity of a neurotoxic effect. We test the behaviour of zebrafish at 6dpf because it is much more stable and reproducible than at 5dpf. The molecular markers we aim to develop as a final product can eventually also be measured at 5dpf or earlier, so outside of Directive 2010/63.	EAWAG	Address the gaps in zebrafish behavioural assays as a measure of neurotoxicity by analysing concomitant cellular, structural and molecular changes in the nervous system during exposure and recovery. Evaluate whether behavioural tests could be beneficially incorporated into the hazard assessment of neurotoxic substances, for example as an add-on to the zFET OECD 236. The data obtained will also contribute to the development of AOPs converging on neurotoxicity and behavioural outcomes.

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Zebrafish embryo test	Danio rerio	We investigate developmental neurotoxicity in zebrafish embryos and larvae via behavioural tracking and brain histopathology	SDU	Developmental neurotoxicity is not specifically investigated in any of the existing OECD TGs using fish. If DNT-endpoints could be included in OECD fish TGs, the regulation of chemicals affecting DNT and causing adverse population relevant effects on for example behaviour or brain could be identified and regulated.
Assessment of neurotoxicity and multigenerational effects on reproduction in Caenorhabditis elegans	Caenorhabditis elegans	A multi-generational exposure of age synchronized Caenorhabditis elegans is carried out and the reproductive capacity is evaluated by counting the progeny by using microscopical high content analysis. Neurotoxic effects are evaluated on exposed C. elegans at behavioural level and transgenic strains with DAergic neurons tagged by green fluorescent protein with dopamine transporter-1 promotor are used to visualize the bodies and processes of DAergic neurons.	UPO	Neurotoxicity and multigenerational effects on reproduction should be adequately investigated among BPA and analogues. Neurotoxicity and effects on reproduction are major regulatory endpoints and simple <i>in vivo</i> assays using Caenorhabditis elegans can be very useful
Planarian regeneration assay	Girardia tigrina	Effects of compounds are evaluated by changes in head regeneration of decapitated planarians (regeneration of photoreceptors and auricles, blastema growth). Malformations and teratogenic effects are assessed. Tests can be adapted for acute, chronic, neurobehavioural, reproductive, and developmental toxicology. Water only exposures.	UAVR	Adaptation of assays with planarians to infer on possible developmental / teratogenic effects of BPA alternatives. The test can be used as an alternative to assays with vertebrates.
Fish embryo test (OECD TG236)	Danio rerio	Evaluation of lethality, malformations and embryo development. The test will be complemented with heart rate and behaviour analysis.	UAVR	Optimization of FET assay to assess behavioural effects of BPA alternatives in zebrafish embryo model. The test can be used to reduce/replace animal experimentation (later stages).

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Behaviour toxicity assay with tadpoles of <i>Xenopus laevis</i>	<i>Xenopus laevis</i>	Evaluation of the capacity of tadpoles to detect chemical contamination and avoid it. The median avoidance concentration will be computed.	UAVR	Additional ecological relevance to complement the data generated by the FETAX assay in assessing the hazards of BPA alternatives, namely behavioural responses in <i>Xenopus laevis</i> tadpoles. The test can be used to reduce and refine animal experimentation.
Fish embryo test (based on OECD 236) with additional endpoints related to Developmental Neurotoxicity (DNT)	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	We will develop AOP-based NAMs that use zebrafish embryos for ED-related DNT. Essential building blocks are already available in endorsed AOPs leading to DNT in mammals, and their applicability in fish will be investigated. OECD Test Guideline 236 for the Fish Embryo Acute Toxicity (FET) Test will be used as a basis for the development of these AOP-based NAMs. We will add endpoints that provide more information on DNT, selected based on key events (KEs) relevant to DNT. These could include for example brain development, neurosensory development (e.g., eye development, neuromast development) and/or behaviour. We will use model compounds for AOP and endpoint development, and bisphenol (alternatives) as test compounds.	UAntwerpen	Currently, there are no zebrafish embryo assays for assessing ED-related DNT. Such an assay would be very valuable to inform both on environmental and human health. The AOP-based endpoints will be used to support the development of IATAs. The development of NAMs that are based on existing OECD test guidelines with the addition of endpoints that are supported by OECD endorsed AOPs will significantly accelerate the development of IATAs for ED. The data on BPA alternatives will be of direct relevance to REACH and will serve as a case study for improving the assessment of endocrine disruptors in general.
Zebrafish embryo assay for identifying chemicals inducing ataxic gait: Z-EmbryoGait	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>) up to 5 dpf	Z-Embryos Gait is an assay based in the exposure of zebrafish embryos from 72 to 120 hpf to the chemicals and then to analyse potential alteration in the stereotyped kinematics of the vibrational-evoked escape using specific hardware and software	CSIC	The current knowledge on chemicals impairing gait is very limited and only a few numbers of chemicals have been identified (rotenone, MPTP, manganese...). By using the proposed assay new neurotoxic chemicals should be identified and the real hazard of this groups of chemicals should be characterized.

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
ELEA _ Early exposure_short and Late Effects Assay	Xenopus laevis (embryo)	<p>This assay connects early exposure and transcriptomic signatures to adversity. The principle of this assay is to link endocrine activity (Mode of Action) and neuronal adversity within a unique assay. Exposure starts from 2 cell stage for 5/7 days (depending on the temperature) and ends at the same developmental stage as XETA (TG248 Xenopus Eleutheroembryonic Thyroid Assay). Brain transcriptome and the motility are the short-term effects that we studied. We will study the effects of other hormonal pathways (Estrogens, Androgens, Glucocorticoids and their dedicated antagonists) than the thyroid one and the late effects of developmental exposure to Estradiol, Testosterone, Dexamethasone, T4 (and the agonists) + the BPA alternatives</p>	CNRS	<p>The ELEA assay is building an AOP on a single assay, a molecular initiating event (with transcriptomics signatures), an adverse outcome (cognitive defects, motility etc) and the plausibility between the two. Furthermore, this assay is addressing EATS modalities and Retinoid X Receptor (RXR). The ultimate goal of this assay is to predict early stage (<i>in vitro</i>) effects without having to perform the long-term adversity-related effect (the whole analysis). Currently there are TG 231 and TG248 (Tier 3) and TG 241 (Tier 4) for thyroid modalities. There is a crucial need to have more Tier 4 assays (addressing adversities) in the interim, with the ultimate goal to only perform the first part of the assay (early exposure and transcriptomic) to be predictive of adversity once the whole AOP is validated.</p>
Endocrine disruption				
EASZY assay (TG250)	tg (yp19a1b: GFP) Zebrafish embryos	<p>tg (cyp19a1b: GFP) zebrafish embryos are exposed to test chemicals (Bisphenols) from fertilization for 96 hours in order to assess the time and concentration dependent effect on the ER-signalling pathway though <i>in vivo</i> imaging of GFP driven by the ER-regulated cyp19a1b promoter and RT-PCR on ER-regulated genes (e.g. esr).</p>	INERIS	<p>To generate data on the effect of Bisphenol on the emergence of the ER-signalling pathways in embryos and to develop a TK model to link predicted internal exposure concentrations with brain aromatase expression.</p>

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Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Ciona embryo-larval bioassay for effect testing of HPT axis disrupting chemicals	Ciona intestinalis type B	The Ciona embryo-larval bioassay to be considered established and used in this study will most likely resemble the one described by Bellas et al. (2003) "A standardisation of Ciona intestinalis (Chordata, Ascidiacea) embryo-larval bioassay for ecotoxicological studies." Water Research 37(19): 4613-4622. It would require further testing/adaptation/optimization of including: rearing conditions (e.g., temperature, salinity, pH, sperm/egg ratio, and embryo density), exposure approaches (e.g., static, semi-static, flow-through, concentrations, test duration, replication, single stressors, mixed stressors), targeted effect assessment (i.e., MOA characterisation and adverse outcome assessment), broad-content analysis (e.g. omics) and high-content (high-throughput) screening (e.g. semi-automatization of image analysis etc.).	NIVA	Development of a Ciona embryo-larval bioassay for use in testing the effects of chemicals that interfere with hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis signalling (GnRH-GnRHR pathway). There is a significant lack of non-vertebrate test methods for marine taxa, particularly in relation to chronic toxicity assessment and early life stages. The use of ascidians for early life stage ecotoxicity testing is a promising approach to increase knowledge of EDC-related effects in marine invertebrates and may provide a more ethical alternative to the use of vertebrates such as fish in EDC testing, for example for potentially thyroid disrupting emerging chemicals such as bisphenol A replacement chemicals.
Ciona embryo-larval bioassay for effect testing of HPT axis disrupting chemicals	Daphnia magna	Daphnia magna acute assays following the OECD Test guideline 202, and modified to determine gene expression profiling, disruption of moulting through interference with the ecdysone receptor, chitin synthesis and chitin-degradation and neuro(endocrine) pathways. The testing principles would ideally adopt to AOP events defined in already proposed AOPs relevant for crustaceans.	NIVA	A suite of assays that can be used to rapidly and predictably identify the moulting disruption potential of compounds and populate the existing network of AOPs (AOP#4, #16, #161-162, #358-#361) remains to be developed to support regulatory testing and to extend the coverage of current testing strategies for endocrine disruption, developmental toxicity and neurotoxicity testing in crustaceans.
Modified nematode test according to ISO standard 10872:2020, in 96-well format	Caenorhabditis elegans	The ISO standard 10872:2020 provides the basis for the assay, but instead of 12-well 96-well plates are used for the exposure. Modified is also the culture of the worms in liquid medium instead of agar plates, as recommended by the ISO 10872:2020. Standard phenotypic endpoints (mortality, growth, reproduction) are combined with RNAseq based transcriptomics and behavioural endpoints.	BfG	<i>In vivo</i> ecotoxicity testing using (as yet) unprotected model organisms such as <i>C. elegans</i> can address pressing regulatory needs: acute and chronic, low cost testing, covering all developmental stages, reproduction and multiple generations (<i>C. elegans</i> has a short life cycle of less than two days, is very small and a self-fertilising hermaphrodite - no sex bias), and testing

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				the same organism in different media (soil, sediment, water).
OECD TG 243 Lymnaea stagnalis reproduction test	Lymnaea stagnalis	OECD TG 243 is investigating reproduction by counting (cumulative) number of clutches during 28d exposure. We investigate endocrine sensitive endpoints including hormone concentrations and developmental effects in the embryo generation	SDU	No endocrine specific endpoints are investigated in the only TG using molluscs. Regulators have no tools to request data on endocrine disruption in molluscs. It is urgently needed to include endpoints sensitive to endocrine disruption to be able to protect molluscs.
Assessment of the endocrine effects of chemicals on insects.	Coccinella septempunctata	The assay will assess the effects of chemicals on invertebrates' endocrine system and more specifically the effects on ecdysis process of insects, by using standard bioassays in combination with molecular, analytical and -omics techniques. The assay will include morphological assessment, gene expression analysis, analytical measurements and metabolomics or/and proteomics analysis.	BPI	Endocrine disrupting effects on invertebrates and specifically on arthropods are only assessed through reproduction studies that do not specifically address ED related endpoints. The results are used for the enrichment of the existing AOPs or the development of new AOPs. In addition, this assay, following appropriate validation and relevance assessment, can be incorporated in the testing strategy for the assessment of possible endocrine effects of chemicals on non-target organisms.

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Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Zebrafish embryo assay that includes transcriptomic assessments to evaluate potential adverse effects of BPA & BPA alternative compounds	Zebrafish eleutheroembryos (Danio rerio)	This assay exposes zebrafish eleutheroembryos from 96 to 120 days post fertilization to BPA or BPA alternatives to assess changes in transcriptomic biomarkers of exposure.	CSIC	The assay implements transcriptomic analysis in regular zebrafish toxicity testing. This approach will allow to increase the knowledge of the complex responses by assessing 20-25 biomarkers of exposure in a single zebrafish assay. This approach will provide a better knowledge of potential effects of exposures since it will allow to assess effects of different biological functions simultaneously.
Xenopus Eleuthero embryonic assay (XETA)	Xenopus Eleuthero (embryo)	This assay is an embryonic assay on xenopus laevis. It uses a transgenic line Tg [<i>thibz</i> : eGFP] which allows the quantification of thyroid-hormone-mediated transcriptional activity. This assay has been validated by the OECD in 2019.	CNRS	The TG 248 is a Tier 3 assay (mode of action). The conclusion is thyroid hormone system disruptor or not. We plan to do more co exposure eg (+/-) T4, with deiodinase inhibitors, with glucuronide inhibitors to fine-tune the mode of action. As a regulatory assay and as batteries of assays are developed, XETA could be included in a battery of assays for thyroid modality.
Metabolic disruption				

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Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Modified nematode test according to ISO standard 10872:2020, using axenic liquid culture	Caenorhabditis elegans	<p>To grow <i>C. elegans</i> on axenic medium instead of <i>E. coli</i> allows the analysis and modification of <i>C. elegans</i> nutrition and eliminates <i>E. coli</i> as a confounding factor during toxicant exposure.</p> <p>The fat metabolism of the nematodes is linked to longevity and aging, and there is evidence fat accumulation can easily be studied microscopically due to the transparency of the worms (<i>C. elegans</i> have no adipocytes and store fat in droplets mostly in their intestinal cells) and fat regulatory pathways are conserved (and can be analysed by transcriptomics). <i>C. elegans</i> is therefore an amenable model to study metabolism disruption.</p> <p>The analysis of the metabolome (MS-based metabolomics) is planned.</p>	BfG	<p>Elucidation and improved understanding of interrelationships between the regulation of fat metabolism, obesity and endocrine disruption. These are easier to study in a "simple" organism like <i>C. elegans</i>. It is suggested that many <i>C. elegans</i> fat regulatory pathways play similar roles in mammals.</p> <p>To increase application of alternative, "simple" models and invertebrate species to screen for disruptive effects on metabolism, the endocrine system or the development of the nervous or the immune system.</p>
Lymnaea stagnalis embryo test	Lymnaea stagnalis	<p>Development and pre-validation of an invertebrate NAM for endocrine/metabolic disruption in developing molluscs (<i>L. stagnalis</i>)</p> <p>We are investigating a number of potential endpoints to be included in this draft embryonic/developmental test. It is running from fertilized egg until hatch (around 14 days) and includes morphometric/developmental endpoints as well as histopathological endpoints. We also analyse thyroid hormones (already identified in juvenile <i>L. stagnalis</i>). A number of endocrine related genes are also currently investigated.</p>	SDU	<p>No endocrine specific endpoints are investigated in the only TG using molluscs. Regulators have no tools to request data on endocrine disruption in molluscs. It is urgently needed to include endpoints sensitive to endocrine disruption to be able to protect molluscs.</p>
Assessment of obesity effects and oxidative stress in <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	Caenorhabditis elegans	<p><i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> are treated for the adequate exposure time period, fixed by 60% isopropanol and then stained with Oil-Red-O. Quantitative analysis of lipid deposits can be conducted by microscopical high content analysis or by decolorizing the Oil-Red-O staining with absolute ethanol. In parallel, green fluorescent protein transgenic strains with genes related to oxidative stress and lipid metabolism are evaluated for their mRNA expression through fluorescence measurement.</p>	UPO	<p>There are contradictory findings about the possible involvement of oxidative stress and other mechanisms of action of BPA and analogues. The obesity effects of bisphenol and analogues has not been adequately investigated.</p> <p>Obesity effects should be considered from a regulatory point of view and simple <i>in vivo</i> assays using <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> can be very useful.</p>
Immunotoxicity				

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Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Assessment of the impact of stressors on Zebrafish microbiome-immunity axis	Zebrafish	The current paradigm in systems toxicology show that the key aspect of health is balanced microbiome-immune-gut axis. The complex approach that would analyze the adverse impact of environmental stressors on this axis is now being developed employing multi-omics approach.	MU	The approach for a comprehensive assessment of the impact on the complex microbiome-immune axis is not yet fully developed. Despite this, the deregulation of the microbiome is a crucial factor, currently not recognized by AOP. Establishing confidence in microbiome-related assays could enhance existing AOPs or even spark the development of new ones. Such assays could also be integrated into testing strategies for evaluating the adverse effects of chemicals on immunity, as the microbiome has a significant influence on the immune system.
Reproductive toxicity				
OECD TG 243 Lymnaea stagnalis reproduction test	Lymnaea stagnalis	RNA-sequencing of adult Lymnaea stagnalis to characterize the transcriptome and identify candidate biomarker genes for toxicity.	SLU	There is a general lack of knowledge of the Lymnaea transcriptome. This test will help the identification of target genes and will increase the knowledge of toxicity in gastropods.
Acute toxicity tests with daphnia for survival and reproductive output under multiple stress of BPA alternatives, pesticides and environmental stress	Daphnia magna	Daphnids are exposed to a range of Bisphenol S concentrations for 21 days to assess the effect on survival and reproduction. In addition to BPS, daphnids are exposed to pesticides and food limitation to analyse the lethal and sub-lethal effects under field realistic multiple stress conditions. The effects will be predicted with Stress Addition Model (SAM)	UFZ	In the environment, toxicants and environmental stressors are present and act together. Such joint effects are therefore of great importance but are generally not assessed. Effects at the level of the whole organism also include latent effects in most cases. So far, only long-term studies can detect such delayed effects. The SAM should make it possible to detect such effects based on short-term <i>in vivo</i> tests. The approach suggested directly supports the need for a field relevant effect

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				assessment in various EU regulations (Guidance Document on Risk Assessment, Commission Directive 93/67/EEC, Regulation (EC) No 1488/94 and Directive 91/414/EEC).
Various				
Frog embryo teratogenesis assay Xenopus (FETAX - ASTM E-1439)	Xenopus laevis (embryos)	Evaluation of malformations, development and growth in amphibian embryos.	UAVR	Complement FETAX assay to assess BPA alternatives mode of action in Xenopus embryos. A set of biomarkers related with oxidative stress, neurotoxicity and other relevant endpoints will be performed to complement FETAX assay. The test can be used to reduce/replace animal experimentation (later stages).
Assessment of cardiotoxicity, neurotoxicity and metabolic disruptive effects of BPA in Daphnia magna	Daphnia magna	(1). D. magna Nile Red assay that visualizes storage lipid accumulation in lipid droplets; (2) Changes in D. magna heartbeats able to assess cardiotoxicity; (3) High-throughput D. magna locomotion and phototactic changes upon light stimuli that may inform us for neurological disruptive effects on stimuli perception and on locomotion activity.	CSIC	There are few if any toxicity assays addressing cardiotoxicity, neurotoxicity and metabolic disruptive effects in non-vertebrate species. This test can provide a more comprehensive toxicity assessment procedure able to detect specific effects linked to AOPs.
Lymnaea embryo toxicity test /LSET	Lymnaea stagnalis	Development of an embryo toxicity test using newly fertilized snail embryos based on methodology from zebrafish embryo toxicity tests.	SLU	Currently, there are no standardized embryo toxicity tests on aquatic gastropods. Results will increase the knowledge on invertebrate developmental toxicity. It will help the development of a standardized protocol for Lymnaea stagnalis embryo toxicity.

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Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Daphnia magna standard acute and chronic tests	Daphnia magna	Based on the literature review and results from the performed standard bioassays supported with the <i>in silico</i> model predictions, the selection of BPA alternatives, which are suitable as model chemicals for the development of specific NAMs, will be performed. Specific biomarkers (such as neurotoxicity, oxidative stress and other relevant endpoints) will be taken into account for further NAM development. All these experiments will be performed in close cooperation with our <i>in silico</i> group and in combination with chemical analysis.	UG-PL	Currently, there is no regulation on the investigation on such specific endpoints addressing neurotoxicity, oxidative stress or other disruptive effects in non-vertebrate species such as crustacean. Exploring the application of such endpoints in the toxicity testing may lead to the proposal of alternative and simple method using invertebrate species for more comprehensive toxicity assessment procedure, reducing/replacing number of experiments on vertebrate species.
Artemia salina standard test	Artemia salina			

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type/ format	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
<i>In vitro</i> assays					
Neurotoxicity					
Automated cellular neurotoxicity assay	differentiated SH-SY5Y Cells	384 square well plate	Cell assay for neurotoxicity of environmental pollutants and of environmental samples in a high-throughput cellular assay that detects cytotoxicity of differentiated neuronal cells and the neurite outgrowth by imaging methods that quantify neurite length.	UFZ	Over 1000 environmental samples have been measured with this assay since its development in 2021 and, to our knowledge, it is the only neurotoxicity assay other than acetylcholine inhibition that has been used to test environmental samples. The assay has potential for use in water quality monitoring and chemical hazard assessment because it is high throughput and not disturbed by matrix effects. For water quality monitoring, effect-based trigger values would still need to be developed.
Automated acetylcholinesterase inhibition assay	differentiated SH-SY5Y Cells	384 square well plate	Cell assay for acetylcholinesterase inhibition of environmental samples in high-throughput that is not disturbed by co-extracted organic matter and allows the characterisation of environmental pollutants.	UFZ	The assessment of environmental samples with the isolated enzyme acetylcholinesterase is quite popular but co-extracted organic matter leads to false positives and this problem is overcome with this cell based assay, which uses the naturally occurring AChE in differentiated neuronal cells to probe the AChE activity with a classical Ellman's assay. The assay has potential for use in water quality monitoring and chemical hazard assessment because it is high throughput and not disturbed by matrix effects. For water quality monitoring, effect-based trigger values would still need to be developed.

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type/format	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
MitoOxTox	AREc32	384 square well plate	Reporter gene assay AREc32 that detects cytotoxicity and the activation of oxidative stress response and is multiplexed with mitochondrial membrane inhibition measurements based on high-content imaging methods. Method under development but promising results in high throughput.	UFZ	The assay has potential for use in water quality monitoring and chemical hazard assessment because it is high-throughput and provides three endpoints - cytotoxicity, activation of the oxidative stress response, and mitochondrial toxicity. Effect-based action levels would need to be developed for water quality monitoring.
Endocrine disruption					
YES assay	Saccharomyces cerevisiae	yeast cells - In solution	This assay uses a genetically modified Saccharomyces cerevisiae, which contains the gene for the human estrogenic receptor coupled to a reporter gene. Activation of the receptor leads to the expression of the reporter gene product (β -galactosidase), which converts the substrate CPRG (yellow colour) to CPR (red), which is measured in a spectrophotometer microplate reader.	UAVR	This assay is commonly used in monitoring studies and our work focuses on making adaptations so that it can be used as a predictive tool to infer on the potential estrogenic activity of BPA alternatives. These adaptations include the expression in concentration units (rather than estradiol equivalents) and the conversion of ABS into generated products during the chemical reaction. It can be used as a screening tool for estrogenic-like-effects.

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ELEA _ Early exposure_short and Late Effects Assay	Xenopus laevis		This assay has been developed within the two projects ATHENA and ENDPOINTS (Eurion cluster). The principle of this assay is to link endocrine activity (Mode of Action) and neuronal adversity within a unique assay. Exposure starts from 2 cell stage for 5/7 days (depending on the temperature) and ends at the same developmental stage as the XETA assay (TG248 Xenopus Eleutheroembryonic Thyroid Assay). Motility is measured at 2weeks post fertilization (and one week after exposure stops). At 3 weeks post fertilization, brain structure and mainly neuron/glia ratio is measured to connect late effect on brain structure with early brain gene expression dysregulations. In PARC we will study late effects of developmental exposure to Estradiol, Testosterone, Dexamethasone, T4 (and the agonists) + the BPA alternatives	CNRS	<p>The ELEA for its early exposure links brain transcriptomic analysis (list of 20 to 50 genes) to adversity. Thus, we aim at identifying key modulators of each hormonal axis (or common to several axis but still fulfilling ED properties).</p> <p>The regulatory application is quite straight forward as the list of these identified genes could be used as a chore list for identification of endocrine disruptors. We could imagine a chip that detects the different hormonal pathways that are disrupted based on the expression results of these genes (like API Strips for the metabolic skills of micro-organisms). The list of genes could also be validated in other systems (cells, zebrafish for example).</p>
Metabolic disruption					
Thiazolyl blue tetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay	Male of Xenopus laevis	XTC-2 (Pudney, Varma and Leake, 1973) fibroblasts derived from a <i>X. laevis</i> tadpole, or A6 (Rafferty, 1969b) (ECACC - 89072613) epithelioid cells derived from the kidney of an adult male <i>X. laevis</i> . - 2D	Assay that uses a colorimetric method to assess cell viability. MTT is a positively charged tetrazolium compound that can readily penetrate viable cells, where the tetrazolium salts are reduced into formazan crystals.	UAVR	This assay provides complementary information on the toxicity of BPA alternatives. It is a high through put methodology that can reduce and replace the use of animal testing in the initial toxicity screening of BPA alternatives.

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type/ format	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Zebrafish liver spheroids to determine toxicity and metabolic disrupting activity of BPA analogues	Zebrafish	ZFL (zebrafish liver cells) - 3D cell culture: ZFL spheroids; 96-well plates	Cell viability (live/dead cells) and ATP content to characterize the metabolic activity of spheroids after acute (24h)/chronic (2 weeks) exposure. To improve the predictability/sensitivity of the assays, the concentration of the compounds in culture medium/spheroids will be analysed. This will allow referring the effects to the experimental concentration of the compounds rather than the nominal concentrations.	CSIC	Cellular responses under acute/chronic exposure scenarios can be understood using this assay. It also more accurately recapitulates the <i>in vivo</i> state as the cell morphology, cell interactions, architecture and exposure to toxicants more closely resemble those of native tissues.
Zebrafish liver spheroids to determine toxicity and metabolic disrupting activity of BPA analogues	Zebrafish	ZFL (zebrafish liver cells) - 3D cell culture: ZFL spheroids; 96-well plates	Analysis of the lipidome of the spheroids together with transcriptomic responses of a selected set of genes involved in lipid metabolism will allow detecting the ability of BPA analogues to act as metabolic disrupters and to obtain markers of adverse effects on liver function (steatosis, fibrosis, inflammation)	CSIC	Lipidomic/transcriptomic alterations induced by BPA analogues can provide essential information on molecular initiating events (MIEs). Using the AOP approach in combination with the development of novel bioassays to integrate biomarkers could fill data gaps in cases where finding a suitable, data-rich chemical or biological analogue may not be feasible and expand the use of NAMs in ERA. These assays more accurately recapitulate the <i>in vivo</i> state, as the cell morphology, cell interactions, architecture and exposure to toxicants more closely resemble those of native tissues.

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type/ format	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Photosynthetic efficiency	Periphytic community	green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria, bacteria, fungi, protozoa, micro-meiofauna	Natural periphytic communities are exposed to up to 7 concentrations of selected contaminants in 96 well plates for 4 to 24h, at pertinent time of exposure (e.g. 1h, 4h, 24h), photosynthetic activity of each well is measured by Pulse-Amplitude-Modulation fluorometry using Imaging-PAM. Dose-response models are then fitted to the observed data to determine acute toxicity thresholds for selected contaminants on photosynthetic activity at community level. This acute toxicity test can also be used to characterize tolerance acquisition of communities adapted to contamination.	INRAE	Such measurement will provide information about the impact of chemical pollutants on microbial metabolism of the autotrophic component within the community. This may have ecological consequences due to the role of the photosynthesis in the carbon cycle and primary production
Enzymatic activities	Periphytic community	green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria, bacteria, fungi, protozoa, micro-meiofauna	Natural periphytic communities are exposed to up to 7 concentrations of selected contaminants in 96 well plates for 4h. Substrate associated with a fluorochrome is added to each well to measure the activities of up to 3 extracellular bacterial enzymes involved in key biogeochemical processes (beta-glucosidase for C cycle, leucine amino-peptidase for N cycle and phosphatase for P cycle). After 4h of exposure, fluorescence measurements are performed to determine enzymatic activities. Dose-response models are then fitted to the observed data to determine acute toxicity thresholds for selected contaminants on bacterial activities at community level. This acute toxicity test can also be used to characterize tolerance acquisition of communities adapted to contamination.	INRAE	Such measurement will provide information about the impact of chemical pollutants on microbial metabolism of the heterotrophic component within the community. This may have ecological consequences due to the role of these enzymatic activity in organic matter decomposition, detoxification and overall C, P, N cycles.

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type/ format	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Metabolism screening	Periphytic community	green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria, bacteria, fungi, protozoa, micro-meiofauna	After exposure of periphytic communities to selected contaminants in appropriate setups (from small aquaria to channels mimicking river flow), periphytic communities are sampled and quenched. Thereafter, metabolites are extracted, separated by chromatography and analysed. Results are further analysed using a workflow under W4M environment followed by benchmark dose derivation by using DROMICs. Each step of this method will be optimised in the specific activity “High throughput metabolomics in aquatic periphyton” to provide SOPs for (1) HT exposure of periphyton for metabolomics analysis, (2) HT sample preparation of periphyton for metabolomics analysis, (3) the semi-automatic data processing and analysis of metabolomics data.	INRAE	Overall, the development of HT metabolomics on periphyton will contribute to filling the regulatory gaps on the microbial community towards a comprehensive assessment of the toxicity of chemicals at the community level that may endanger aquatic ecosystems functions and sustainability. Beyond aquatic systems, this project will provide proof of concept of the relevance of microbial communities, which is critical in the one-health context according to the crucial role of microbiome in environmental, animal and human health. Also, the workflow developed in this action may be further applied to another microbiome.
Non-Genotoxic Carcinogenicity					
Assessment of gap junctional intercellular communication by multiparametric scrape-loading dye transfer (mSL-DT) assay	Rodent (Fisher 344 rat)	WB-F344 (rat liver epithelial/oval cells) - 2D	The assay measures levels of gap junctional intercellular communication (GJIC) mediated through connexin proteins, a physiological process whose inhibition has been linked to mitogenic signalling and other tumour promoting mechanisms activated by non-genotoxic carcinogens.	MU	The assay covers the inhibition of intercellular communication associated with disruption of tissue homeostasis (no validated assay is currently available). It is part of a battery of tests (defined approach or IATA - this endpoint is included in the IATA proposed by the OECD expert group for NGTxCs hazard identification: Jacobs et al., PMID: 32594184)

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type/ format	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
micronucleus assay on ZFL spheroids	Zebrafish (adult <i>Danio rerio</i>)	zebrafish liver cell line ZFL (from normal adult zebrafish liver) - 3D ZFL culture - ZFL spheroids	The cytokinesis block micronucleus assay (CBMA) is one of the most widely used methods in genetic toxicology, evaluating genomic stability. By applying it on an advanced 3D <i>in vitro</i> model system is intended to increase the test validity and predictability.	NIB	This assay will be established and optimised over the course of the project to address clastogenic/aneugenic potential data, improve environmental risk assessment and comply with the 3Rs.
toxicogenomics assay on ZFL spheroids	Zebrafish (adult <i>Danio rerio</i>)	zebrafish liver cell line ZFL (from normal adult zebrafish liver) - 3D ZFL culture - ZFL spheroids	The toxicogenomic approach enables insight into cellular responses and altered pathways as the result of exposure to hazardous agents and possible mechanisms of action. Again, by applying it on an advanced 3D <i>in vitro</i> model system intended to increase the validity of the data.	NIB	Mechanisms of action resulting in potential genotoxic effects can be addressed by this assay, improving the environmental risk assessment and following the 3Rs principle.
multilabeling of biomarkers for different genotoxicity endpoints for flow cytometry on ZFL spheroids	Zebrafish (adult <i>Danio rerio</i>)	zebrafish liver cell line ZFL (from normal adult zebrafish liver) - 3D ZFL culture - ZFL spheroids	Multiple simultaneous genotoxicity biomarker labeling, enables simultaneous detection of several relevant genotoxicity endpoints, providing a screening platform, using ZFL spheroids, The model will be established and optimized during the duration of the project. This is a promising model that is intended to provide more physiologically relevant data with higher predictivity.	NIB	Screening for genotoxicity endpoints in an ecotoxicologically relevant model can be addressed by this assay, improving the environmental risk assessment and following the 3Rs principle.

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Assay title	Test species	Cell type/ format	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Comet assay on ZFL spheroids	Zebrafish (adult <i>Danio rerio</i>)	zebrafish liver cell line ZFL (from normal adult zebrafish liver) - 3D ZFL culture - ZFL spheroids	The comet assay is one of the classic methods in genetic toxicology, enabling the detection of different types of DNA damage as a response to genotoxic stimuli. Developing and optimizing it to be used on advanced 3D models will take the test to the next level, bridging the gap between <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> .	NIB	Data on DNA damage induction in an ecotoxicologically relevant model can be addressed by this assay, improving the environmental risk assessment and following the 3Rs principle. Potentially contributing to the test's acceptance in the OECD standards. Applying a fish spheroid model makes the test ideal for use in ecotoxicological studies.

Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
<i>In silico</i> assays				
PBTK-TD model coupled to EASZY assay	Zebrafish	Due to the small size of the zebrafish embryo, internal concentrations are difficult to measure, while internal exposure is required to better understand dose-response relationships. Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models deal with this issue, allowing the estimation of the chemical spatio-temporal distribution in a biological model that is undergoing rapid morphological and physiological changes. PBPK-Toxicodynamic model will link internal concentration and the aromatase B induction in ZF embryo to characterize the risk associated with chemical exposure.	INERIS	PBPK-TD models for ZFE experimental assays allow the consideration of multiple confounders and linking of TD endpoints to internal exposure. It also provides a practical tool for designing new experiments, and predicting the nominal exposure concentration to achieve a desired internal dose. Finally, it has the potential to provide concentrations in organs, which means that it can be used in future research that provides this type of measurement, necessary for a complete understanding of TK and its integration into risk assessment.

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Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
PBTK-TD of biomarker responses	Stickleback, Zebrafish (juvenile and adult)	Physiologically based toxicokinetic models coupled with toxicodynamics (PBTK-TD) have proven to be valuable tools to fill the knowledge gap between external exposure and effect dynamics. The aim of the current work was to explain the impact of BPA on the immune response by determining its temporality. In addition, the relationship between BPA dose and these responses was investigated using this model.	INERIS	The PBTK-TD model of biomarker responses makes it possible to understand and characterise the dynamics of these physiological parameters currently used in biomonitoring. This allows to reduce the uncertainty caused by confounding factors, in particular the different temporal dynamics of biomarkers obtained under the same exposure conditions, and ultimately to better characterise the risk.
VEGA HUB	Fish (LC50 acute toxicity)	Models: SarPy/IRFMN, KNN/ReaD ACROSS, NIC, IRFMN,	UG-PL	There is no relevant predictive model for estimating aquatic toxicity (OECD 202) for compounds in the BPA group and their alternatives. The developed model: 1) will provide insight into the potential mechanism of BPA aquatic toxicity, 2) will allow estimation of the class of the toxicity of potential BPA alternatives considered to be less hazardous to the environment. A QSAR model is under development for estimating the aquatic toxicity of BPA (in accordance with the OECD 202 guideline). Using this model, it will be possible to predict the aquatic toxicity of alternatives to BPA and gain insight into their mechanisms. The developed model can be implemented in open-source tools (OECD QSAR Toolbox, Vega) and used for safety assessment for regulatory purposes.

Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
PBTK modelling		Data collection of biological, physiological and toxicological variables to calibrate and develop TK tools and biologically-based models for environmental risk assessment of relevant environmental species and selected chemicals. We will investigate a generalized framework for PBTK model development for environmental risk assessment, develop ontology and semantics for environmental PBTK models keeping the structural differences with the predominant mammalian TK. Regarding environmental risk assessment specific issues like, bioaccumulation and biomagnification of pollutants, will be addressed within an environmental toxicokinetics modelling framework.	IISPV	Recently, a number of PBTK models have been developed to model the ADME processes for pharmaceuticals, environmental contaminants and pesticides, applicable to a wide range of substances and different organisms. The models provide estimates of chemical concentrations over time in specific tissues based on descriptions of the ADME processes and the physiology and anatomy of the organism. PBTK models have become essential in <i>in silico</i> risk assessment tests as they provide a mechanistic framework for understanding toxicological effects in organisms. However, the acceptance of these <i>in silico</i> assays for regulatory purposes has been limited due to the lack of harmonisation of these models and the lack of a generalised modelling approach that can address the problem of environmental risk assessment.
Stressor Addition Model (SAM)	Any	The sensitivity of organisms does not only depend on the toxicity of the chemical to which the organisms are exposed. Toxicity also depends strongly on the presence of other stressors. The Stressor Addition Model (SAM) quantifies the joint effects of toxicants and additional stressors. The assessment is based on results from <i>in vivo</i> test systems under optimal conditions and results of the effect of the additional stressor under control conditions. The joint effects of toxicants and additional stressors can be predicted. In addition, SAM enables the prediction of the mortality-related latent effects of toxicants on invertebrate populations. Their relevance is shown by the fact that, especially at low concentrations, such latent effects contribute the most to the overall effect	UFZ	In the environment, toxicants and environmental stressors are present and interact. Such combined effects are therefore of great importance but are generally not assessed. In most cases, effects at the level of the whole organism also include latent effects. So far, only long-term studies can detect such delayed effects. The SAM should make it possible to detect such effects on the basis of short-term <i>in vivo</i> tests. In order to place biocidal products on the market, it is necessary to determine concentrations that will not cause unacceptable effects in the “real” environment. In addition, the effect assessment must cover the entire life-time of an organism (Guidance Document on Risk Assessment, Commission Directive 93/67/EEC and Regulation (EC) No 1488/94). Similarly, the EU Uniform Principles for the assessment of plant protection products require that no registration should be granted unless it can be demonstrated that “... under field

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Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
				<p>conditions no unacceptable impact on the viability of exposed organisms..." (Annex VI, Directive 91/414/EEC). Field conditions include multiple stressors and the consideration of latent effects. Accordingly, the proposed approach directly supports the need for field-relevant impact assessment in various EU legislation.</p>
MLTox	<p>203 species from the taxonomic groups of fish, crustaceans, and algae. Current focus on fish (140 species)</p>	<p>Assessment of application of Machine learning methods to predict aquatic ecotoxicity outcomes. We identify the potential and limitations of this approach and its adaptation to chemical hazard assessment.</p>	<p>EAWAG MUI</p>	<p>The potential of machine learning to predict ecotoxicological outcomes is currently underexplored and prone to errors in proper implementation (data leakage, reproducibility, reporting, interpretability). This is unfortunate as the technology has a high potential to complement, if not ultimately replace, animal testing. We are working towards the regulatory use case of replacing the OECD TG 203 for hazard assessment with a machine learning model and making the model as understandable as possible by analysing which factors (specific chemical groups, species sensitivity differences) contribute to high and low performance indicators. This will be done to identify potential data gaps that could further improve model performance.</p>
Environmental databases and bioinformatics tools	<p>Environmental species (algae, aquatic macrophytes,</p>	<p>Use of various effect databases and bioinformatics tools (incl. SSDs, classical toxicity endpoints, OMICS, structural similarity tools etc.) to develop identification of toxicity mechanisms of relevance, populate the</p>	<p>NIVA</p>	<p>Consistent and standardised use of effects data, ontologies and controlled vocabularies is limited. Organisation of and reuse of data to populate hazard characterisation is therefore required to facilitate rapid and comprehensive description of the knowledge domain and</p>

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Assay title	Test species	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
	crustaceans, fish, molluscs, ascidians)	knowledge domain and perform cross-species extrapolations.		identification of knowledge gaps. Reuse and/or cross-species extrapolation and/or analysis of existing data for hazard characterisation is envisaged to facilitate characterisation of the existing knowledge, support chemical read-across and avoid duplication/reduce redundancy of testing efforts. Cross-species extrapolation would allow greater use of data to fill data gaps.
VEGA HUB	Fish (chronic NOEC)	Model: IRFMN	NIC	These tests fill some <i>in silico</i> gaps in the environmental toxicity of BPA alternatives and will contribute to the regulatory acceptance of the <i>in silico</i> models available in VEGA.
	Fish specific (Fathead minnow, guppy)	Models: EPA, KNN/IRFMN		
	Daphnia magna	Models; EPA, DEMETRA, IRFMN		
	Algae	Models: IRFMN, ProtoQSAR/Combase		
	Bee (acute toxicity)	Model: KNN/IRFMN		

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Assay title	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
<i>In chemico</i>			
OPERA and OECD QSAR Toolbox	Rapid screening and prioritisation of large lists of chemicals using some of the existing QSAR tools relevant for environmental species	NIVA	Several QSAR tools are being developed and their consistent use to characterise potential toxicity and toxicity mechanisms, and to link them to physico-chemical properties, is required through collaborative efforts. QSAR methods are already in use and well established as screening and prioritisation tools in integrated testing strategies and to extend the knowledge domain. The proposed contribution, together with initiatives undertaken by others, would ensure a solid set of expertise in QSAR methods available for PARC.

Assay title	Short description	Contributing partner institution	Regulatory input
Other			
Review of Environmental Toxicology Databases for acute fish and daphnia neurotoxicity data	We analyse available ecotoxicity data for acute mortality in fish and identify to which degree the effect values for invertebrates can be considered protective towards fish to serve as a pre-screening for neurotoxic compounds. Ultimately, a machine learning model could be developed to flag potentially neurotoxic compounds for further testing to replace this test.	EAWAG MUI	Current alternative methods to the acute fish test (fish embryo and fish cell tests) do not appear to be sufficiently sensitive to chemicals with neurotoxic MoAs. We need to understand the extent to which the daphnids are more sensitive than fish anyway and may therefore overcome this limitation of the alternative methods. In addition, we need to understand whether the classification's M-factor based stratifications of acute aquatic toxicity may not be suitable considering the variability of acute toxicity data. Martin Paparella (MUI) is leading the OECD project to develop an IATA for acute aquatic toxicity, where this knowledge is urgently needed.

Annex II

Validation-related activities within PARC to progress new methods and approaches for hazard and risk assessment of chemicals

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Context

An important ambition of PARC is to facilitate and accelerate the transition of new approach methodologies (NAMs) for toxicological hazard and chemical safety assessment into regulatory practice. Ultimately, one important measure of the success of PARC will consist of the tangible positive impact PARC will have made on regulatory processes and decision-making contexts. In WP5 ('Hazard Assessment') and WP6 ('Innovation in regulatory risk assessment') of PARC, there are a substantial number of projects underway aimed at tackling different challenges and priorities with regard to NAMs and integrated approaches, each with its own specific objectives and strategies but all aimed at making new approaches fit to use in regulatory practice. This document aims to delineate the scope of these WPs with regard to validation.

Why validation?

A key requirement for the regulatory application of any NAM or integrated approach is not only that it is fit-for-purpose but also that it is sufficiently robust and reproducible, in short reliable. This is usually established by validation. Validation is a scientifically anchored process that serves to demonstrate the reliability and relevance of a method for a particular purpose, building trust and confidence, within a regulatory context of use.

Although validation is an essential requirement for regulatory application of new toxicity testing methods, it's not sufficient in its own right, since there are also several other factors that contribute to building confidence within regulatory and stakeholder communities. Over many years and also recently, various 'confidence frameworks' have been put forward. These are intended to provide a framework structure to help integrate NAMs into testing strategies to increase regulatory readiness and achieve regulatory acceptance and uptake in different decision-making contexts. That said, appropriately designed validation activities are often central to producing much of the scientific evidence that feeds into these confidence building frameworks. Many NAMs in regulatory use have been subject to validation exercises and peer review. However, one has to be aware that not all NAMs that are currently in regulatory use have been subjected to validation. In fact, many longstanding *in vivo* methods can only refer to their long history of use instead. One prominent context for conducting validation studies is the development of OECD test guidelines. These guidelines underpin the OECD policy of Mutual Acceptance of Data (MAD) and as a consequence, they are required to be highly standardised, applicable within a wide range of industrial sectors and international regulatory systems, and implementable under Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) in test facilities throughout OECD member countries. Thus, the OECD guidance document on validation (GD34¹) sets out certain expectations on how a validation study should be conducted to demonstrate that a new test method meets these requirements, although there is clear provision for validation approaches to be adapted to match the purpose or intended use of the method

context. Whilst GD34 is currently being revised, any potential revisions of the guidance will not impact on the relevant work within PARC, because PARC is not conducting full ring trials.

An important complementary route to test guideline development, to employ new testing and assessment approaches in hazard and risk assessment, is to enhance the usability of data produced within academic studies that use non-guideline methods, where the results are typically published in peer-reviewed scientific journal articles. Regulatory use of such literature requires a critical weight of evidence assessment. In fact, many regulatory decision-making contexts already try to make use of such data in their assessment processes since within the EU, it is a legal requirement in most sectors that all existing data be considered in hazard and risk assessment. However, the main challenge to exploit this route is to improve the quality, reliability, relevance, transparency and availability of data produced by non-guideline tests through various means, including weight of evidence assessment, and also tailored proof-of-concept studies, together with demonstrating readiness for test guideline development and regulatory application.

In the assessment of contaminants or cosmetics, some NAMs already play a central role in hazard identification and characterization, and critically, for the latter, they have been validated. For other groups of regulated compounds such as the active substances of biocides, plant protection products, and pharmaceuticals, a comprehensive set of test guideline-based animal studies is required. Here, NAMs are used for mechanistic analysis, e.g. to identify endocrine active properties. Likewise, there are ongoing attempts to use NAMs for grouping and justification of read across.

PARC activities related to scientific validation and building confidence in new methods and approaches

There are different work streams within PARC (WP5 and WP6) that may contribute to the validation and regulatory acceptance (regulatory readiness) of new methods and approaches to hazard and risk assessment (see Figure 1).

Development of NAMs for specific key events

There are five endpoints for which specific NAMs are developed in WP5: non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, metabolic disruption, thyroid disruption, immunotoxicity and (developmental) neurotoxicity.

All of these endpoints are complex and cannot be covered by a single NAM; instead, batteries of relevant NAMs are needed. For some of the abovementioned endpoints NAM have already been under development and promising NAMs have been identified within and outside PARC, which need further work to improve regulatory readiness. This is also being addressed in validation training for PARC partners. For other endpoints, more basic research is needed.

Figure 1. The general work streams within PARC (WP5 and WP6) contribute to the validation and regulatory acceptance (regulatory readiness) of new methods and approaches to hazard and risk assessment.

Development of integrated approaches to testing and assessment for specific health effects

For complex health effects, such as systemic toxicity, it is typically the case that individual *in vitro* or computational methods are not adequate in their own right to satisfy information requirements. Thus, it is necessary to combine them within an integrated approach to testing and assessment (IATA), following extensive guidance and case studies provided by the Working Party on Hazard Assessment and the Test Guidelines Programme at the OECD. Developing and evaluating IATA is an iterative process that requires working on multiple interrelated levels in parallel, including mechanistic design (e.g. using Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs; see OECD webpage), method selection and optimisation, validation of individual components, and evaluation of overall IATA performance. There are several projects within or outside PARC that are working together towards IATA for particular health effects of regulatory concern, such as genotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, immunotoxicity, endocrine disruption, and developmental neurotoxicity. Since the basic designs of the different IATA are still a subject of research and development within PARC and elsewhere, current initial efforts are focused on ensuring individual methods are optimised and reliable within the developers lab and that they demonstrate sufficient sensitivity and specificity for the mechanistic effect (key event, in AOP terms) they represent. As such, efforts related to the development of IATA will yield outcomes and data that ultimately contribute to validation.

Development of assessment methodologies for (new) mechanistic data streams

Data derived from new experimental tests and computational models need to be processed, combined and interpreted to satisfy information requirements and to arrive at a regulatory decision. In order to minimise the requirement for expert judgement within these steps, which can introduce inconsistencies in outcomes and prove difficult and expensive to implement in practice, PARC is undertaking several projects to develop and evaluate bioinformatics-enabled algorithms, workflows and assessment methodologies to automate the data-to-decision pipeline as much as possible. Particular attention is being given to omics data streams. Although these data can be potentially very information rich, they currently require highly specialised expertise to process and interpret. This has severely hampered their standardisation and subsequent widespread application in regulatory hazard and risk assessment. The development of these assessment

methodologies not only relies on innovative design approaches and tools, but it also requires establishing inter alia their internal and external validity for a defined purpose and contexts of use.

Case studies to demonstrate new approaches and their potential regulatory application

Optimal evolution and adaptation of regulatory information requirements and assessment processes, to make the best use of new hazard and risk assessment methods and approaches, requires considerable engagement between the regulatory community, developers, and end-users, and this interaction is expected by the Commission. As proven over the years by e.g. several EU funded projects and the APCRA (Accelerating the Pace of Chemical Risk Assessment) initiative, hazard and risk assessment case studies are a very effective vehicle to facilitate such engagement in a practical and productive manner. Such case studies may provide proof of concept and can help explore the applicability range for new methods. Close collaboration between researchers and regulators in the definition, conduct and review of case studies not only increases familiarity with NAMs and integrated approaches, but also provides a basis for co-design of solutions that meet regulatory needs, and ultimately builds confidence in their performance and application. A common feature of many case studies is to evaluate the performance of the employed methods and approaches against expected outcomes, using well-characterised reference chemicals for example. Such activity will inherently initially focus on feasibility, relevance and fitness for purpose, with reliability or robustness being assessed subsequently in case a method or approach shows particular promise.

Frequently asked questions and corresponding replies:

Q: Does PARC perform any validation of NAMs for hazard and risk assessment of chemicals?

A: Yes, it does. Various activities that are part of a validation process are conducted in several projects, which are supporting the development of IATA, assessment methodologies and case studies. However, while PARC will try to bring its methods to regulatory readiness, according to accepted test method readiness criteria and, with the support of a validation methodology lead, full formal validation is not in the remit of the partnership, nor would this be feasible in the current structures.

Q: Why isn't PARC currently conducting any ring trials of new *in vitro* methods?

A: PARC is not planning to conduct ring trials, because full validation is not one of its goals. Ring trials are typically conducted within the context of validation studies to develop OECD test guidelines, since there is a requirement for test guidelines to be reproducible and transferable so they can be used in test facilities throughout OECD member countries. Whilst there are currently no ring trials in the PARC WP, depending on the willingness of the partners to contribute to future proposals for ring trials, this may evolve.

Q: Will PARC propose the development of any OECD test guidelines?

A: No, this is currently not foreseen. Following protocol at the OECD, it is up to OECD member countries, and collaborative consortia to propose the development of a test guideline that they think would satisfy regulatory needs across different sectors and jurisdictions. So, in principle at least, one or more EU member countries, or the European Commission as a member organisation, could propose the development of new guidelines based on the results or deliverables of PARC, or conduct such work within PARC going forward.

Q: What will happen to the IATAs developed within PARC, how will they be used?

A: There are several possibilities. First and foremost, the IATAs currently under development in PARC are being designed to address the real world regulatory paradigms that the European regulatory authorities need to address.

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Additionally, the IATAs will be discussed in dedicated stakeholder workshops. They could also be submitted to the IATA case studies project being conducted at the OECD. This would allow them to be evaluated by a large community of international regulators with a view to further improving them and building confidence in their design, performance and application. Depending on the degree of harmonisation and test method standardisation achieved, the IATAs could provide a basis for the prioritisation of which NAMs to validate further for OECD test guideline purposes. As an alternative, or in parallel, guidance on how the IATA could be used for regulatory purposes could be developed at the EU or international level.

Q: Will PARC identify methods that are ready for OECD test guideline development?

A: PARC will certainly, where appropriate, identify methods that may be considered for OECD test guideline development. As a first step, a mapping is performed of the high priority needs of the OECD test guideline programme versus areas where PARC can support these going forward. This overview will provide a basis for future project proposals within PARC in relation to regulatory utility and confidence, including opportunities for contributing to validation.

¹ OECD, Guidance Document on the Validation and International Acceptance of New or Updated Test Methods for Hazard Assessment